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Knowledge Transfer Activity Report 2

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Executive Summary

This Knowledge Transfer Activity Report 2 aims to describe Knowledge Transfer activities undertaken by the **ATLAS** project (May 2016 – July 2020). This report presents the methods, activities, key results and measurable impacts of **ATLAS**.

The **ATLAS** project aims to gather diverse new information on sensitive Atlantic ecosystems, to produce a step-change in our understanding of their connectivity, functioning and responses to future changes in human use and ocean climate. To maximise the impacts of **ATLAS** and its results, the project has implemented effective communication, dissemination and knowledge transfer methodologies and strategies.

Knowledge management and transfer systems applied to the **ATLAS** project were designed to promote efficient transfer of **ATLAS** outputs and results, leading to optimal exploitation. Recognised as a critical process in bringing research forward, with a focus on research being conducted on wider societal and industrial needs, **ATLAS** employed an adapted version of the proven knowledge management and transfer methodology originally developed by AquaTT in the Framework Programme 7 MarineTT project (Grant Agreement No 244164), and further developed and applied by the Horizon 2020 COLUMBUS project (Grant Agreement No 652690). Throughout the project, the **ATLAS** knowledge transfer methodology focused on collecting, analysing and transferring high-potential Knowledge Outputs and Key Exploitable Results.

The **ATLAS** Compendium of Results was developed by AquaTT to capture these Knowledge Outputs, describe the successful knowledge transfer activities carried out across the partnership, and to outline the impact and next steps needed to ensure **ATLAS'** legacy and long-term impact. The key achievements and output studies are presented for each of the four **ATLAS** objectives. Relevant output studies for **ATLAS** end-users and stakeholders across the triple helix of academia, industry and society are identified and constitute the **ATLAS** User Development Group (see p13). Key Exploitable Results are linked to the European Commission's Horizon Results Platform to showcase these results and increase their overall impact. It was previously foreseen that relevant Knowledge Outputs would be taken up in the 'Marine Knowledge Gate' (www.kg.eurocean.org) to ensure visibility and availability to stakeholders; however, as the host was not accepting submissions for immediate upload and combined with the launch of a new platform by the European Commission, the Horizon Results Platform was determined as a more suitable outlet for exploitable **ATLAS** outputs.

This report presents the **ATLAS** Compendium of Results, a professionally designed booklet (web and print versions) summarising **ATLAS'** key achievements, including details on target audience and active

knowledge transfer carried out to reach each of the relevant end users per key output, links to **ATLAS** submissions to the Horizon Results Platform, publications, deliverables, data, communication and outreach resources. A full list of submissions to the Horizon Results Platform is also included here (see Annex 1).

Besides the Compendium of Results being available to download from the **ATLAS** project website, it is also available through Zenodo and the AquaTT website. The **ATLAS** compendium is intended for distribution at several future high-level events (e.g. upcoming events as part of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and the Fourth session of the Intergovernmental Conference) facilitating further dissemination of **ATLAS'** exploitable outputs, extending the impact and legacy of **ATLAS'** work even further.

The team involved in deliverable writing: AquaTT

Acknowledgements: The **ATLAS** Compendium of Results was designed and developed by AquaTT, with significant contributions from **ATLAS** partners. The authors gratefully acknowledge input received from these results owners.

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ATLAS Compendium of Results

Unlocking the Potential of the Deep Atlantic Ocean

The next pages present the **ATLAS** Compendium of Results booklet published by AquaTT in June 2020.

Contributors: The **ATLAS** Compendium of Results booklet was designed and developed by AquaTT, with significant contributions from **ATLAS** partners. All results described were generated by the **ATLAS** project. Content writing, compilation, editing, design and infographic development was carried out by AquaTT – Annette Wilson, Peadar O’Raifeartaigh, Keegan Porter, Sive Finlay, Anne-Marie Williams and Marieke Reuver with input from the **ATLAS** Project Office (UEDIN) Julia Eighteen, Georgios Kazanidis, J Murray Roberts and **ATLAS** result owners.

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COPELUM

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ATLAS COPELUM OF RESULTS - INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

The North Atlantic Ocean is a key marine region that comprises fragile, beautiful and essential ecosystems, from deep cold-water corals to hydrothermal vents. It provides goods and services that are essential for our well-being. Exploitation of these goods and services has been a key driver for growth and wealth creation. However, this fragile environment is under threat.

Almost 150 years since the *HMS Challenger* Expedition, still very little is known about deep ocean ecosystems, their roles as reservoirs of biodiversity and genetic resources, or their health under future scenarios of climate change and human exploitation. Large-scale ocean observation is needed to improve our understanding of marine ecosystems, their biogeographic patterns, biodiversity, biogeochemistry, ecosystem services, and the goods they support. The capacity to model, understand and predict shifts in the dynamics of North Atlantic ecosystems will support preservation and will enable sustainable production of new products and industrial applications.

In response to these needs, in 2015 the European Commission launched the 'Blue Growth' call under the Horizon 2020 programme, calling for ideas and plans from research consortia to improve the preservation and sustainable exploitation of Atlantic marine ecosystems, to which ATLAS responded.

Launched in 2016, over a four-year period ATLAS has explored the world of deep-sea habitats (200 – 2000 m) and generated a wealth of diverse knowledge on deep-Atlantic ecosystems.

THE MIGHTY ATLANTIC OCEAN IS A PLACE LIKE NO OTHER.

AT A GLANCE

TITLE: A trans-Atlantic assessment and deep-water ecosystem-based spatial management plan for Europe (ATLAS)

CALL: Blue Growth: Unlocking the potential of seas and oceans (H2020-BG- 2015-2)

TOPIC: Improving the preservation and sustainable exploitation of Atlantic marine ecosystems (BG-01-2015)

INSTRUMENT: Research and Innovation Action

DURATION: May 2016 – July 2020 (51 months)

CONSORTIUM: 25 partners plus one linked 3rd party, from 12 countries

COORDINATOR: The University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, Scotland, UK

ATLAS PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Centred around four primary objectives, ATLAS has created a strengthened knowledge base, advanced understanding of deep-sea functioning and connectivity, improved capacity to predict the response of deep-sea ecosystems to future changes in human use and ocean climate, and supported the development of adaptive management plans for sustainable exploitation and use of marine resources in the North Atlantic Ocean basin.

ATLAS METHODOLOGY

Multidisciplinary approach
Through its multidisciplinary approach, ATLAS has achieved a greater understanding of deep-sea ecosystems in the North Atlantic Ocean than ever before. Intensive data gathering, new measurements, and samples from previously unexplored areas have provided essential knowledge on ocean circulation, dynamics, deep-sea ecosystem functioning, biodiversity and biogeography, and connectivity of resources. Through greater understanding of deep-sea ecosystems services and Blue Growth potential, ATLAS has addressed gaps in marine valuation and in its use as an aid to decision making. Networking and collaboration across sectors have supported better monitoring. Together, integrated new knowledge and new data have allowed ATLAS to improve predictive models. Using these predictions, various scenarios of ocean dynamics and cross-sectoral Blue Growth, an adaptive Atlantic marine strategic planning approach was developed.

ATLAS case studies
ATLAS assembled 12 case studies to assess Blue Growth potential at the trans-Atlantic basin scale, and to incorporate the diversity of sensitive deep-water ecosystems. Following the major Atlantic current patterns, these case studies covered a wide biogeographic, regulatory and jurisdictional range, and regions encompassing Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs), Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs) or Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). These sites were selected based on proximity to Blue Growth activities, presence of focal ecosystems, availability of existing data or samples, and opportunities for offshore expeditions.

The case studies have allowed ATLAS to integrate diverse data sources (including information on ocean circulation, ecosystem functioning, biological diversity, genetic connectivity and socioeconomic values), to predict deep-sea ecosystem response to shifts in human use and climate change, and to develop management strategies that focus on sustainable Blue Growth. A full breakdown of ATLAS case studies can be found on pages 10 to 11.

ATLAS CASE STUDIES

ATLAS BLUE GROWTH SECTORS

- Fisheries
- Oil & Gas
- Tourism
- Biotechnology
- Seabed Mining

ATLAS CASE STUDY 1
LOVE OBSERVATORY (NORWAY)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, ERMEX, ULDEN
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: Cold-water coral (CWC) reefs, sponges
Due to its remote continental shelf, this area is described as the gateway to the Barents Sea. It is a transitional zone and the cold water coral (CWC) sponges, which form extensive bottomward reefs in this area.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 2
PAROE-SHETLAND CHANNEL (UK)
COLLABORATORS: LEEDS, BP, ODAK, MMS
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: Sponge grounds
This area's unique morphology leads to diverse benthic assemblages. Within the beds are found cold-water sponges and cold-water corals, which are important for commercial fisheries. A distinct sponge belt occurs between depths of 400-800 m.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 3
ROCKALL BANK (UK - IRELAND)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOD, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs, coral gardens, sponges
Enhanced oceanographic circulation around the Rockall Bank leads to high biological productivity and diverse benthic assemblages such as sponge aggregations, coral reefs and sponges and production of cold-water sponges. An Ecologically or Biologically Significant Area under the European Council Directive.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 4
MINGULAY REEF COMPLEX (UK)
COLLABORATORS: LEEDS, MMS
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs
This reef system comprises a 300-200 m depth deep, distinctive rocky outcrop that extends the continental shelf out to 7000 metres. It is the only reef in the world that is open to the sea for long time and making it part of a 'Global Reef System'.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 5
PORCUPINE SEABIGHT (IRELAND)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOD, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs, coral gardens, carbonate mounds, sponge grounds
This area is a unique deep-sea environment, with a high level of biological productivity. It is a transitional zone between the shelf and the deep-sea. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 6
BAY OF BISCAY (FRANCE)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC on slope and in canyon settings
Recent studies have confirmed the occurrence of cold-water coral habitats in this Bay. The genetic optimum of coral reef diversity between the Bay and the Mediterranean Sea has been identified. This area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 7
GULF OF CÁDIZ, STRAIT OF GIBRALTAR, ALBORÁN SEA (SPAIN - PORTUGAL)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOW, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs, coral gardens, sponge grounds
This region is a transitional zone between the shelf and the deep-sea. It is a rich area of biological diversity and productivity. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 8
AZORES (PORTUGAL)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOW, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: Hydrothermal vents, CWC reefs, coral gardens, sponge grounds
This area is a rich area of biological diversity and productivity. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 9
REYKJANES RIDGE (ICELAND)
COLLABORATORS: IOD
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: Hydrothermal vents, CWC reefs, coral gardens, sponge grounds
Our understanding of the effects of oxygen on the composition and distribution of life and the diversity of life in the deep-sea is enhanced by the study of the Reykjanes Ridge. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 10
DAVIS STRAIT (CANADA AND GREENLAND SEA)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOW, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs, coral gardens, sponge grounds
The Davis Strait is known for its complex hydrography. A high level of biological productivity is observed in the area. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 11
FLEMISH CAP (CANADA)
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOW, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: Coral gardens, sponge grounds
Flemish Cap is an offshore bank located in the Area Beyond National Jurisdiction within the Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization region. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS CASE STUDY 12
MID ATLANTIC CANYONS
COLLABORATORS: BIOD, IOW, IOW, IOW
FOCUS ECOSYSTEMS: CWC reefs on slope and in canyon settings
The topography and geology of the Atlantic canyons and banks are rich in biological diversity. The area is rich in deep-sea sponges and other organisms.

ATLAS PARTNERS & THIRD PARTY

1. THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM (UK)	11. IODINE (US)	21. THE ARCTIC UNIVERSITY OF NORWAY (NO)
2. AARHUS UNIVERSITY (DK)	12. ROYAL NETHERLANDS INSTITUTE FOR SEA RESEARCH (NL)	22. THE SCOTTISH ASSOCIATION FOR MARINE SCIENCE (UK)
3. IOWA INSTITUTE OF SEA (USA)	13. DYNAMIC EARTH (US)	23. SEASCAP CONSULTANTS (UK)
4. SECRETARIA REGIONAL DO MAR, CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA (BR)	14. SEAFORD UNIVERSITY (UK)	24. UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA (ES)
5. BRITISH GEOLOGICAL SURVEY (GB)	15. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN (IE)	25. UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA WILMINGTON (US)
6. BIRNIE CONSULTANTS (UK)	16. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK (IE)	26. BIRNIE BELLEVILLE (UK)
7. INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER (FR)	17. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND (IE)	27. AQUAT DEEP (UK)
8. MARINE SCOTLAND SCIENCE (UK)	18. UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL (UK)	28. BIRNIE BELLEVILLE (UK)
9. UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL (UK)	19. UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHERN DENMARK (DK)	29. FISHERIES AND OCEANS CANADA (CA)

Knowledge Transfer
Communication and dissemination of ATLAS results have been integral components of the ATLAS approach, ensuring widespread awareness, engagement with the public and targeted transfer of ATLAS knowledge to all users. Recognised as a critical process in bringing research forward, with a focus on research being conducted on wider societal and industrial needs, ATLAS employed an adapted version of the proven knowledge management and transfer methodology originally developed by AquaT1 in the Framework Programme 7 MarieTT project (Grant Agreement No 244854), and further developed and applied by the Horizon 2020 COLUMBUS project (Grant Agreement No 652690). This methodology was integrated into the ATLAS project design, allowing knowledge to be fast-tracked to target and end-users. This ensured the timely delivery of key knowledge outputs and results to ATLAS stakeholders, accelerating and facilitating greater impact.

Throughout the project, the ATLAS knowledge transfer methodology has focused on collecting, analysing and transferring high-potential knowledge outputs and key Exploitable Results. The ATLAS consortium, as a whole, has participated in a variety of communication, dissemination and knowledge transfer activities across the triple helix of academia, industry and society. Key messages and results from ATLAS have been presented to stakeholders at conferences and events, published in high-impact scientific journals, and informed policy processes and discussions. Exploitation workshops have facilitated two-way dialogues and transfer of ATLAS knowledge to industrial stakeholders, while the use of open-access data management platforms ensures pioneering ATLAS research is accessible beyond the project, creating an impactful legacy.

ATLAS END-USERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

This table identifies relevant stakeholders and end-users for the key knowledge outputs presented as output studies in this compendium. Please note this is not an exhaustive list.

ATLAS end-users and stakeholders	ATLAS knowledge outputs
SCIENTISTS, RESEARCHERS, ACADEMICS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output study 1.1: Weakening of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) through the industrial era p19 Output study 2.1: Cold-water coral and sponge physiology database p28 Output study 2.2: New approach to identify the key environmental parameters that control cold-water coral ecosystem performance p29 Output study 4.2: New climate model projects major impacts on coral and commercially important fish habitats in the deep Atlantic due to climate change p48
POLICY MAKERS, DECISION MAKERS, OCEAN GOVERNANCE ADVISORS, REGULATORY BODIES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output study 3.1: Approaching the assessment of Good Environmental Status in the deep sea p37 Output study 3.2: Current deep-sea Area-Based Management Tools are unprepared for climate change p39 Output study 3.3: New evidence to support the protection of deep-sea sponge ecosystems at Tropic Seamount p41 Output study 4.1: Novel Marine Spatial Planning decision support protocol p46 Output study 4.2: New climate model projects major impacts on coral and commercially important fish habitats in the deep Atlantic due to climate change p48 Output study 4.3: Contribution to the development of NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets p50
BLUE ECONOMY, BLUE GROWTH INDUSTRIES (AQUACULTURE, TOURISM, BIOTECHNOLOGY, TRANSPORT, ENERGY, MINING) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output study 1.2: An expert assessment of risks posed by climate change and anthropogenic activities to ecosystem services in the deep-sea p30 Output study 2.5: Using eDNA and quantitative PCR to assess biodiversity in the open ocean p31 Output study 4.3: Contribution to the development of NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets p50 Output study 4.1: Novel Marine Spatial Planning decision support protocol p46 Output study 4.2: New climate model projects major impacts on coral and commercially important fish habitats in the deep Atlantic due to climate change p48
GENERAL PUBLIC, EUROPEAN, CANADIAN AND AMERICAN CITIZENS, MARINE EDUCATORS, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT EXPERTS, TEACHERS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output study 1.3: Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS - The ATLAS educational outreach portfolio p22

ACHIEVEMENT 1: ATLAS ADVANCED
Understanding of deep Atlantic marine ecosystems and populations

- Atlantic Ocean circulation: New measurements from the Eastern Subpolar North Atlantic. The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation is weaker today than ever 1000 years ago.
- Insights into cold-water coral population history.
- Ecosystem engineer control theory: Seabed topography formed by cold-water corals can focus food supply.
- Deep-sea ecosystem services in the North Atlantic are impacted by human activities. Deep-sea ecosystems are at risk to climate change.
- Society recognises the value of these services and supports new marine management plans.
- >30 benthic communities discovered: cold-water coral gardens, deep-sea sponge grounds, hydrothermal vents.
- 'Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS' Outreach educational programme.
- 34,000+ direct engagements at Dynamic Earth.

ACHIEVEMENT 2: ATLAS IMPROVED
Capacity to monitor, model and predict responses of deep-sea ecosystems to future change

- New methods and approaches: Using eDNA and quantitative PCR to assess biodiversity in the open ocean. Non-invasive oxygen flux measurements. Mapping coral reef biomass. Identifying key environmental parameters that control cold-water coral ecosystems performance. Indicators for monitoring vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems.
- Low cost deep-sea imaging systems.
- Hydrodynamic, biogeochemical and habitat suitability models.
- An index: multi-criteria assessment - for identifying Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems & Biodiversity hotspots.
- Cold-water coral and physiology database.
- Area-based resource management plans.
- Predicted habitat suitability Maps: >50% of cold-water coral habitat at risk.
- Contribution to NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets as a piece of Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization's Roadmap for an ecosystem approach to fisheries.
- Industry data sharing & revised business practices: Love Observatory (Equator) & West of Scotland (BP).

ACHIEVEMENT 3: ATLAS TRANSFORMED
Data and transformed new knowledge for effective ocean governance and sustainable exploitation

- 'Luso' hydrothermal vent field declared as Marine Protected Area by the Regional Government of the Azores.
- ATLAS science policy panels x3.
- ATLAS policy briefs: 'climate-proofing' the Marine Protected Area network in the North Atlantic Ocean.
- Good Environmental Status and biodiversity assessments.
- Contributions to UN negotiations on an international, Legally Binding instrument on the conservation and sustainable use of marine Biodiversity in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction.
- ATLAS GeoNode: www.atlas-geonode0300.eu. Discover, Visualise, & Download ATLAS Data.
- A series: deep-sea features that meet Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas criteria submitted to the Convention on Biological Diversity.
- Geological Areas criteria: Gulf of Cadiz, Iberian Spur, Azores Spur, Phoenix, Charlie-Gibbs, Phoenix Zone, Southern Bight, and Rockall Bank & Bank.

ACHIEVEMENT 4: ATLAS DEVELOPED
And tested sustainable adaptive management strategies for deep-sea resources stimulating Blue Growth

- Blue Growth scenarios tested in ATLAS case studies.
- Novel Marine Spatial Planning decision support tool.

OUR REACH

- Hosted 35+ workshops & conferences.
- 200+ peer-reviewed publications (including papers in Nature and Science).
- 25 countries & 12 countries.
- 40+ research expeditions.
- >105m have been reached by ATLAS media coverage.
- Participation in 450+ conferences, workshops and events.
- 70+ workshops, 10 PhD students.
- 12+ new species discovered including Atlantic atlantida.
- ATLAS videos, film and YouTube channel with 300+ videos.
- 20+ press releases.
- 39k+ & 5.4k+ in social open-access Research Topic in Frontiers in Marine Science, Mapping Deep-sea Ecosystems of Ocean State Scale.
- >10 exhibitions.
- Transatlantic cooperation Canada EU/USA.
- ATLAS results have reached: 2K people in policy, 2K people in industry, 2K members of the scientific community.

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

1 Advance

Our understanding of deep Atlantic marine ecosystems and populations

ATLAS advanced our understanding of deep Atlantic marine ecosystems and populations by collecting and integrating high-resolution measurements of ocean circulation with functioning, biological diversity, genetic connectivity, and socioeconomic values.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND ACTIVITIES

- 1. Deep-sea discoveries:** ATLAS partners discovered and described more than 30 benthic communities, including cold-water coral reefs and gardens, deep-sea sponge aggregations and hydrothermal vents in the North Atlantic. ATLAS has contributed to the identification of at least 12 new or putative new species to science, including the discovery of a bivalve, *Myomera atlantana* (dedicated to the ATLAS project) at mud volcanoes on the northern Gulf of Cadiz. The team has also found approximately 35 new records of species in areas where they were previously unknown.
More information: D3.3 bit.ly/2WZKLO1 | Full species list on p62 | **Contact:** Tormo Morato, Marina Carneiro-Silva, IMAS-UIZ | Jose Rueda, IEO | Elean Kinningson, DFO.
- 2. Implications of climate change for global deep-sea benthos:** This 2017 review provides the first comprehensive overview of the impacts of changing environmental parameters on deep-sea floor ecosystems. The work details how such changes, combined with other anthropogenic stressors, will further impact deep-sea floor ecosystems. Possible societal implications were also reviewed. Conducted by ATLAS researchers together with trans-Atlantic collaborators, this work acts as a key reference and increases understanding of climate change on deep-sea ecosystems globally.
More information: bit.ly/3ctJz24 | **Contact:** J Murray Roberts, UEDIN.
- 3. Evidence that ocean currents in the North Atlantic have slowed dramatically:** ATLAS researchers have published studies, including a Nature paper showing significant weakening of surface and deep ocean currents, including the Deep Western Boundary Current and the subpolar gyre, which are part of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. These changes caused unprecedented ecosystem shifts in the industrial era with wide-ranging impacts on species distribution and ecosystem functioning.
More information: bit.ly/2to3Kf1 | **Contact:** David Thornalley, Peter Spooner, UCL.
- 4. In-situ measurements from the eastern subpolar North Atlantic:** A one-year study through ATLAS collaboration with the Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program (OSNAP) and EU H2020 ATLANTOS project. The samples and data from the ELLET Array are the first long-term measurements from the area and contribute to fundamental baseline oceanography.
More information: D1.7 bit.ly/2TjQj0E | **Contact:** Claire Johnson, Stuart Cunningham, SAMS.
- 5. Understanding drivers of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) variability:** The Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program (OSNAP) was launched in 2014 to provide an observational basis for the intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. The first results from the OSNAP array, published in Science with contributions from ATLAS researchers, reveal that processes east of Greenland determine AMOC variability, rather than those in the Labrador Sea as previously thought. The measurements

changed global understanding of the AMOC and contribute to fundamental baseline oceanography.
More information: go.nature.com/2LXXAJw | **Contact:** Stuart Cunningham, SAMS

- 6. Better understanding of deep-sea ecosystem services:** ATLAS has demonstrated the socioeconomic value of deep-sea ecosystems, and the importance of considering these for future Blue Growth. The team assessed the economic and social value of these services and evaluated the risks posed by climate change and anthropogenic activities. Across four case studies in the Azores, Norway, Scotland and Flemish Cap, survey participants conclusively recognised the value of ecosystem services, the current ecological crisis, and the need for sustainable deep-sea management. Despite a lack of familiarity with deep-sea ecosystems, the public support future management strategies with strong preferences for the environment ahead of job creation, prioritising in the following order: marine litter, commercial fish stock health, size of protected areas, and new jobs in future management strategies.
More information: bit.ly/2ZomTuf | bit.ly/2LPD8X0 | **Contact:** Claire Armstrong, IIT.
- 7. Learnings from the Ocean Literacy survey:** Results from Ocean Literacy surveys in the Azores provided measurable insights into public understanding and opinions on the ocean ecosystem services. There is a great deal of public interest in the deep sea, with 77% of respondents stating that their wellbeing is dependent on the deep sea. Understanding what the public knows and perceives about the deep sea allows for meaningful communication, site-specific adapted management strategies, and social acceptability towards specific conservation strategies.
More information: bit.ly/2L0Bo4c | **Contact:** Adriana Bessureucka, IMAS-UIZ.
- 8. New insights into the history of Atlantic cold-water coral populations:** Genetic evidence collected over the last decade has revealed that two species of reef-building cold-water corals, *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*, colonised the North East Atlantic margin after the Last Glacial Maximum (~22,000 years ago) from the West Mediterranean sea through different routes. The results show the impact of past climate change on the distribution and genetic diversity, and fill knowledge gaps on these two species that are structurally essential for Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems.
More information: bit.ly/2z7zUFX | **Contact:** Joana Boinas, Sophie Arnold-Haged, FRESHER.
- 9. Educational outreach programme:** A portfolio of outreach resources was developed for educators, teachers and researchers to advance Ocean Literacy and appreciation of the deep Atlantic Ocean. The portfolio enables life-long learning in people of all ages and backgrounds, and contains free tools and tips which provide innovative ways to communicate ATLAS research and results.
More information: bit.ly/367XK6S | **Contact:** study 1.3 | **Contact:** Hermine Cockburn, Dynamic Earth.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND ACTIVITIES

- 10. Ecosystem engineer control theory for cold-water coral (CWC) growth:** ATLAS researchers have coined a new term to encompass the factors that control CWC distribution in the deep sea. Combining hydrodynamic, biogeochemical and habitat suitability models, they have shown that seafloor topography created by coral frameworks leads to enhanced food supply, showing that corals act as ecosystem engineers. Ecosystem engineer control theory is therefore a more appropriate term than Environmental control theory, used to describe the ability of CWCs to thrive in the food-limited deep ocean.
More information: bit.ly/2Uz2dpx | **Contact:** Karine Soetaert, Dick van Oevelen, WUZ.
- 11. Evidence that human-made offshore structures can improve deep-sea coral expansion:** Using data from industrial stakeholders in the North Sea, this study demonstrates for the first time that anthropogenic structures can support conservation of protected marine species. It also shows that oil, gas and other non-natural installations can help to create highly connected systems by acting as bridges within oceanic coral networks - aiding larvae settlement, improving resilience and supporting ecological conservation. The study highlighted the importance of data sharing and science-industry collaborations, a key feature of the ATLAS project.
More information: bit.ly/2RvYfFA | **Contact:** Lea-Anne Henry, UEDIN.
- 12. Coral larvae dispersal is strongly correlated to atmospheric and ocean circulation patterns:** Results from 40-year particle tracking models show that the dispersal of cold-water coral larvae (*Lophelia pertusa*) are sensitive to atmospheric driven changes in ocean circulation. These findings provide much-needed guidance for establishing well-connected Marine Protected Areas.
More information: bit.ly/3aq7k9k | **Contact:** Alan Fox, SAMS | J Murray Roberts, UEDIN.
- 13. Coral larvae behaviour is species-specific and greatly impacts on ocean connectivity:** ATLAS scientists have shown that coral larvae behaviour, including upward and downward swimming, have a significant impact on dispersal and connectivity in the North Atlantic Ocean. These findings have important implications for future connectivity models and conservation planning.
More information: bit.ly/2YMBt8t | **Contact:** Alan Fox, SAMS | J Murray Roberts, UEDIN.
- 14. Establishing a relationship between Mediterranean outflow Water (MOW) and benthic fauna in the North Atlantic Ocean:** Internal waves travelling at the interface of two different water masses (North Atlantic Central Water and MOW) improve conditions for benthic suspension feeders. These waves result from the impingement of MOW flow against sloping topographies and propagate at the interface of the two water masses.
More information: bit.ly/3eJ0n0G | **Contact:** Angela Mosquera Gimenez, IEO.
- 15. Understanding the importance of spatial scale when distinguishing drivers of change in the deep sea:** ATLAS scientists have shown that the effects of anthropogenic activities can only be separated from natural environmental controls when both small and large spatial scales are assessed in a study area. As human activities are increasingly taking place in the deep sea, the findings of this study highlight the need for similar large-scale analysis to disentangle the complex influences between environmental changes and human impacts on deep-sea ecosystems, an important consideration for marine spatial planners and industry stakeholders such as oil, gas, and mining companies.
More information: bit.ly/30tM6is | **Contact:** Johanne Vad, J Murray Roberts, UEDIN.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

OUTPUT STUDIES

Output study 1.1	Weakening of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) through the industrial era
Description	The AMOC plays an essential role in regulating the Earth's climate through its redistribution of heat. ATLAS researchers from University College London, UK and the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada have found comprehensive evidence of a marked weakening of Atlantic circulation over the past 150 years. The study provides, for the first time, palaeo-oceanographic reconstructions of AMOC over the last 1500 years, suggesting that leading climate models are insufficiently sensitive to certain inputs and could be overestimating stability.
Need addressed	There is an increasingly urgent need to understand deep-ocean ecosystems: their current state, future state, current changing climates and increased exploitation pressures. To better predict future changes in ocean health, associated effects of climate change and impacts of planned activities (e.g. mining), scientists need a strong understanding of ocean circulation.
Approach	By examining the size of sediment grains deposited by deep-sea currents, where larger grains imply stronger currents and vice versa, ATLAS researchers have reconstructed past circulation patterns. The abundance of marine organisms that prefer warm and cold water was then measured in different sediment layers to work out changing near-surface temperatures. Comparing reconstructions with climate change models, ATLAS researchers found evidence that AMOC significantly weakened at the end of the Little Ice Age, around 1850 AD. The results suggest that, at this time, a combination of the onset of the industrial revolution and melting of glaciers and sea ice caused an influx of freshwater that disturbed ocean currents.
Target audience	Scientists, researchers, and academics within and beyond ATLAS who can use the results to further global understanding of ocean circulation and deep ocean ecosystems.
Knowledge Transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nature publication: Thornalley DJR, Oppo DW, Ortega P, Robson J, Brineray CN, Davis R, Hall IR, Moffa-Sanchez P, Rose ML, Spooner PT, Yazhayev I, Keigwin LD (2018) Anomalously weak Labrador Sea convection and Atlantic overturning during the past 150 years. <i>Nature</i> 556, 227-230. doi.org/10.1038/41586-018-0007-4 Presentations at conference and workshops: including Fall AGU, San Francisco (USA), December 2016; PAGES, Zaragoza (Spain), May 2017; UK PACS meeting, Cardiff (UK) September 2017. <p>Science to society</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extensive media coverage: TV news broadcasts on Sky News, BBC and Channel 5, Radio interviews on BBC Radio World at One, BBC 5 Live Up All Night, BBC World Service Morning Show, BBC Radio Wales, NPR podcast, print coverage in The Guardian, The Financial Times, The Washington Post, The Daily Mail, Scientific American, BBC News online.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

Output study 1.1	Weakening of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) through the industrial era
Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nature publication: 5,888 access 87 citations Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 850 + Media reach: 1 million + Longer term impact: Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	We now have evidence that North Atlantic circulation is weaker today than it has been for over a thousand years. ATLAS has provided the first comprehensive ocean-based record to place AMOC in the context of centennial climate change. This has significant implications for future model scenarios on climate resilience and effects on deep-sea ecosystems.
Next steps	UCL and the authors of this work are committed to sharing this new knowledge with others and applying it to develop better ocean circulation and climate model scenarios. Through ATLAS Science-Policy Panel meetings and at future policy meetings (e.g. the 4 th Intergovernmental conference UN General Assembly resolution 72/249) ATLAS continues to inform policy makers about the limitations and accuracy of past and future climate model scenarios.
Contact and contributors	David Thornalley (UCL) ATLAS Partners: UCL, DFO
More information:	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2T03K1F Other: bbc.co.uk/news/science-environment-43713719

Output study 1.2	An expert assessment of risks posed by climate change and anthropogenic activities to ecosystem services in the deep sea
Description	Focusing on the services provided by deep-sea ecosystems, including supporting, provisioning, regulating and cultural services, ATLAS partners have shown that pollution and temperature change pose a high risk to more than 28% of deep-sea ecosystem services, and over 10% are at high risk from ocean acidification and fisheries. Projected negative impacts from temperature change and ocean acidification, fishing, pollution, and oil and gas activities are overwhelmingly more probable than the projected positive impacts. Ecosystem services are not seen to be at serious risk from tourism and blue biotechnology. The services to human wellbeing considered to be most at risk from anthropogenic activities are biodiversity and habitat as supporting services, biodiversity as a cultural service, and fish and shellfish as provisioning services.
Need addressed	The European Commission, under its Blue Growth Strategy, is seeking to support sustainable growth in the North Atlantic across five sectors known as the Blue Economy. To ensure such growth is sustainable, there is a need for greater understanding of deep-sea ecosystems and the various risks to services provided by deep-sea ecosystems. Managing the cumulative impact of human activities is essential to safeguard such services.

Approach	The 'Delphi Approach' was employed to consider the delicate equilibrium between societal needs and environmental sustainability. An interactive expert-based survey was used to assess potential impacts or risks posed by different human activities on deep-sea ecosystems, services in the North Atlantic Ocean from climate change, the Blue Economy, and their cumulative effects.
Target audience	EU and member state policy makers, intergovernmental organisations and policy makers (IPBES, CICES, TEEB), academia, researchers, economists.
Knowledge transfer	Science to science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frontiers in Marine Science publication: Armstrong C W, Vondolia Godwin K, Foley N S, Henry L-A, Needham K, Ressurreicao A (2019) Expert Assessment of Risks Posed by Climate Change and Anthropogenic Activities to Ecosystem Services in the Deep North Atlantic. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> 6, 158. doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00158 Participation in experiments: deep-sea scientists participated in the Delphi Survey between 2017-2018; Round 1 - attendees of the second ATLAS General Assembly, April 2017; Round 2 - online survey for ATLAS project members, October - November 2017; Round 3 - EU H2020 project SPONGES' General Assembly, April 2018. Science to society <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Article in ATLAS Project Newsletter, issue 6, August 2019: bit.ly/3FvguGW
Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frontiers in Marine Science publication: 3,236 views 4 Citations Scientific audience via survey participation: 55 + Newsletter readers: 200 + Longer term impact: Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	Deep-sea ecosystem services in the North Atlantic Ocean are impacted by human activities and are at risk from climate change. ATLAS has shown the importance of considering these services for future Blue Growth and Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) in the deep sea. In addition, services should be considered to inform intergovernmental science-policy decisions (e.g. IPBES, CICES, TEEB) and the development of future frameworks designed to manage and conserve ecosystems and the services they provide.
Next steps	Supporting the development of future frameworks to manage and conserve ecosystems and the services they provide. ATLAS partners are interested in collaborations to implement this work into MSP and future Blue Growth scenarios. Further communication of these findings to researchers and funding bodies should be considered, shaping and unifying future research on the Atlantic deep sea.
Contact and contributors	Claire Armstrong (UIT) ATLAS Partners: UIT, NUIG, UEDIN, UAZ
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2ivlvgld

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 1: ADVANCE

Output study 1.3	Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS - The ATLAS educational outreach portfolio
Description	ATLAS developed a strong educational programme comprising a suite of resources highlighting the importance of the deep ocean and the key methods and achievements of the project. The portfolio contributes to improving Ocean Literacy, and empowering ocean-literate citizens. Topics addressed include ocean acidification, pressure in the deep, technology used in deep-sea exploration, cold-water coral reefs and hydrothermal vents. Educational resources include a large-scale reef survey image, which can be printed for use as a floor mat and allows exploration of a cold-water coral ecosystem at various learning levels in a fun and easy way, augmented reality colouring sheets, and an associated online information portal, were developed to bring three of the ATLAS case studies (P10) to life through the Spectacular app in collaboration with Quaver Visuals Ltd. For other topics, education packs for hands-on experiments were created, including a kit-list, method and background. A script and explanatory film of the Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS interactive show for children, primarily delivered by Dynamic Earth, was produced to support other informal science educators and teachers to deliver the workshop. A Remote Operating Vehicle (ROV) simulator computer game allows people an insight into the work of scientists on board a research vessel and to experience piloting an ROV to explore two further ATLAS case study sites. Licenses were made available to project partners and a 3D model version is available on the ATLAS project website. An animal flow chart "Which deep-sea creature are you?", a 360° video recorded onboard the Canadian icebreaker, CCGS Amundsen, to be viewed with an ATLAS-branded cardboard viewer and 3D coral model of <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> were also produced. An 'Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS' film was created to demonstrate how to run the deep-sea outreach workshop. The resources are freely available to download from the project website, and selected resources are available in English, French, German, Portuguese and Spanish.
Need addressed	Improving public understanding and appreciation of the deep sea are vital steps towards greater conservation and protection of this important ecosystem via informed decision making and societal support for policy development.
Approach	Ocean Literacy is a foundational concept of the Gateway Statement and the Atlantic Action Plan. In line with the Transatlantic Ocean Literacy Implementation Strategy (AORA, 2016), ATLAS has generated unique, dynamic and innovative educational materials to promote and enhance Ocean Literacy. All resources are free to download from ATLAS and are available in several languages, ensuring access for all.
Target audience	Educators, public engagement experts, deep-sea researchers, children, general public.
Knowledge transfer	Science to society <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 'Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS' activities and workshops, in-house public engagement programme at Dynamic Earth, Edinburgh (UK), 2019-2020 Edinburgh International Science Festival (panel presentations and interactive family workshops) April 2017, 2018, 2019 (UK) Science Festival exhibitions throughout the UK including Calthness Science Festival, Scotland (UK), March 2019; Orkney Science Festival, Scotland (UK), August 2019; and Midlothian Science Festival, Penicuik, Scotland (UK), October 2019 Exhibition at 'Science is Wonderful', Brussels (Belgium), September 2019 Amundsen expedition Q&A Postcard Exchange, CCGS Amundsen (Canada) August 2018, 2019 European Research & Innovation Days, Brussels (Belgium), September 2019 European Researchers' Night at the Spanish Institute of Oceanography, Vigo (Spain), September 2019 Articles in ATLAS Project Newsletter, issue 3 (April 2018), 5 (March 2019), and 6 (August 2019): bit.ly/3FvguGW

Knowledge transfer	Science to science / teachers / marine educators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CommOCEAN, Southampton (UK), December 2018 European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA) conference, Newcastle (UK), October 2018 Inspiring STEM learning, Edinburgh (UK), February 2018 EMSEA conference, Azores (Portugal), September 2019 BIG STEM Conference, Edinburgh (UK), July 2019 Irish Ocean Literacy Network meeting, Dublin (Ireland), November 2019 Science to policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation at Scottish Parliament 20th Anniversary Celebration, Edinburgh (UK), June 2019 Resources presented during the third ATLAS Science-Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), May 2019 All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum, Brussels (Belgium), February 2020 Free access to resources for all on the ATLAS website, Dynamic Earth website, Seachange website and Zenodo
Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-house delivery at Dynamic Earth (April 2019 - Present): 26,138 Newsletter readers: 200 + Roadshows, Science Festivals (March 2019 - present): 6,640 + Scientific / teachers / educators: 485 + Policy audience: 30 + Policy/Public audience at the EC 'Science is Wonderful': 3,200 + Total direct engagement: 34,000 + Longer term impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 4: Quality Education
Take home message	An ocean-literate person: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understands the importance of the ocean to humankind Can communicate about the ocean in a meaningful way Can make informed and responsible decisions regarding the ocean and its resources ATLAS has generated unique, dynamic and innovative educational materials to promote and enhance Ocean Literacy for all citizens.
Next steps	The goal of the portfolio is to increase Ocean Literacy for all citizens, so the next steps would be to continue engaging with educators, marine professionals and members of the general public and promote the use of the ATLAS Educational Outreach Portfolio. Dynamic Earth are also committed to embedding some of the Ocean Literacy-focused ATLAS resources into free Continuous Learning and Professional Development online courses for teachers in the UK and are also developing a new exhibition and ocean-literacy programme, "Discovering the Deep" which will feature people and results from ATLAS from April 2021. Further research into European school curricula and link with other initiatives e.g. Blue Schools in Portugal, to facilitate the use of the resources in schools across the globe should also be considered. AquatT will use and promote the portfolio in all future relevant projects and initiatives related to Ocean Literacy, being a founding member of the Irish Ocean Literacy Network.
Contact and contributors	Hermione Cockburn (Dynamic Earth) ATLAS Partners: DE, UEDIN, AquatT
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2z745G0 ATLAS Educational Outreach Portfolio resources: eu-atlas.org/education/education-packs

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 2: IMPROVE

2 Improve

Our capacity to monitor, model and predict shifts in deep-water ecosystems and populations

ATLAS improved the capacity to monitor, model and predict shifts in deep-water ecosystems and populations in response to future change through a better understanding of the connections between physical parameters and biological characteristics to support sustainable exploitation in the North Atlantic.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 2: IMPROVE

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND ACTIVITIES

ATLAS researchers have developed new and improved methods for measuring and monitoring the deep-sea and North Atlantic Ocean including:

- 1. A non-invasive method to quantify oxygen uptake by cold-water corals (CWCs):** ATLAS researchers developed a new non-invasive method that estimates current velocity and dissolved oxygen concentration to quantify oxygen uptake rates of CWC gardens. The results obtained through the new techniques demonstrate that CWCs are important to carbon and nitrogen mineralisation at habitat scale. This provides additional information to help assess the implications of climate-driven shifts in carbon supply for deep-sea ecosystems.
More information: bit.ly/3PpUG57 | bit.ly/2XDNX6A
Contact: Lorenzo Rovelli, Romie N. Giud, USD
- 2. A new approach to map coral reef biomass:** Using a combination of existing data, high-definition video footage, environmental variables extracted from multibeam measurements and respiration data from literature, ATLAS researchers have developed a new approach to estimate the biomass of important cold-water coral reefs. This information is vital to understand their contribution to key processes such as the carbon cycle.
More information: De Cippelle L. (in review) | **Contact:** Laurence De Cippelle, J Murray Roberts, UEDIN
- 3. Low-cost imaging systems to observe the deep sea:** Two custom-made underwater camera systems (live-view drift camera and a stereo-balanced remote video) have been developed by ATLAS partners, in collaboration with the MapGES and Atlantic projects, allowing greater data collection and spatial coverage at a reduced cost. The design and development of both systems will improve capacity to monitor and explore the deep-sea bed and commercially important fish populations.
More information: bit.ly/3dcDuOP | **Contact:** Carlos Dominguez Carrio, Teimo Morato, IMAR-UAZ
- 4. An index to identify biodiversity hotspots:** ATLAS developed a novel multi-criteria assessment method to more objectively identify Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) in the North-East Atlantic Ocean, often biodiversity hotspots. The method evaluates how likely a given area of seafloor is to represent a VME, providing a more systematic and standardised approach (robust and repeatable numeric method) for assessing and identifying VME regions in the North-East Atlantic Ocean.
More information: bit.ly/2VdUu73 | **Contact:** Teimo Morato, IMAR-UAZ
- 5. Common protocols to advance understanding of deep-sea sponge grounds:** ATLAS researchers have published evidence showing that fragile deep-sea sponge aggregations are vulnerable to fisheries and changes in water mass properties, along with a catalogue and suite of indicators to assess their vulnerability and environmental status. Common protocols and procedures were developed to maximise the impact of new technological developments (such as towed cameras and remotely-operated vehicles) to monitor deep-sea sponges and associated ecosystems. This work supports and improves assessments of anthropogenic and climate change impacts in the deep sea, guiding future management and conservation strategies.
More information: bit.ly/34V09J6 | **Contact:** Georgios Kazandis, J Murray Roberts UEDIN
- 6. Coupled hydrodynamic and physiological models to predict deep-sea ecosystem distribution and function:** ATLAS partners have developed a new approach, combining hydrodynamic models and physiological models, to predict coral and sponge distributions, biomass and metabolic activity in deep-sea ecosystems. Results from three ATLAS case studies at Rockall Bank, Condar Seamount and Davis Strait have shown that cold-water corals contribute to biogeochemical cycles and can have a significant impact over large spatial scales.
More information: ATLAS Deliverable 2.4 and 2.5 (see p61) | **Contact:** Dick van Oevelen, NIOZ
- 7. Using eDNA and quantitative PCR to assess biodiversity in the open ocean:** ATLAS partners have developed and tested six species-specific environmental (e)DNA assays. This work demonstrates that eDNA methods can be developed for detecting the presence of target species in pelagic and deep-water environments, and can be used to assess species distributions over space and time.
More information: bit.ly/3c9KUrsee output study 2.3 | **Contact:** Laura Gargan, Jens Carlsson, UCD
- 8. Use of Google Compute Engine to reduce processing time for ocean simulations:** In collaboration with ParallelWorks (a Chicago start-up), ATLAS partners have reduced the processing time for coral larvae simulations from two weeks to one hour by running the calculation via Google Compute Engine. The simulation results provide new insights into how cold-water corals spread across the ocean and show the connectivity of colonies. The workflow design can be adapted and applied by other researchers working on ocean population simulations.
More information: bit.ly/3bcs5R1 | **Contact:** Stefan Gary, Stuart Cunningham, SAMS
- 9. Impact of climate change on food supply and survival of deep-sea ecosystems:** Results from a series of ATLAS experiments on the physiology of cold-water corals and deep-water sponges revealed that cumulative effects of climate change on food supply and ocean acidification impact the distribution and function of corals. This work highlighted that, as a result of climate change, predicted decreases in food availability and responses to ocean acidification will likely impact long-term growth and life cycles of corals. Better understanding of the interactive effects of climate change on deep-sea ecosystems supports accurate monitoring, modelling and future predictions.
More information: ATLAS Deliverable 2.2 (see p61) | **Contact:** Marina Carneiro-Silva, IMAR-UAZ

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OUTPUT STUDIES

Output study 2.1	Cold-water coral and sponge physiology database
Description	Deep-sea cold-water coral (CWC) and deep-water sponge (DWS) ecophysiology and physiology have been active areas of research over recent years, providing previously unknown and valuable new information on these vulnerable ecosystems and facilitating models to predict future scenarios. However, much of the new information and data from scientific publications in this field can be overlooked or is unusable due to factors such as unstandardised units. Addressing this problem, ATLAS partners have assembled existing literature and data into an accessible inventory and database for specific, standardised ecophysiology and physiology processes. The inventory of existing relevant publications lists papers on CWCs and DWSs which supply data on ecophysiology and general papers containing information of the functioning of DWS grounds and CWC reefs. Physiological data for CWC species (<i>Lophelia pertusa</i> , <i>Desmophylia dianthus</i> , <i>Dendrochylia congeria</i> , <i>Mediopora oculata</i> , <i>Antarctic octocorals (Primois Antarctica, Primoisella sp. and Primoisella scotiae)</i> , a sea pen (<i>Pterodites griseum</i>), a CWC from the Pacific (<i>Urimnoea pacifica</i>) and Red Sea corals (<i>Eguchipaximus fistula</i> and <i>Dendrochylia sp.</i>) have been compiled. Data on the following DWS are included: <i>Geodia barretti</i> , <i>Geodia atlantica</i> , <i>Geodia macandrewi</i> , <i>Stylocordilla borealis</i> , <i>Cynastrea antarctica</i> , <i>Mycale acerata</i> , <i>Mycale ingus</i> , <i>Isodyctia kerguelensis</i> , <i>Baikalospongia infermedia</i> , <i>Baikalospongia bacillifera</i> , <i>Phakella ventralbum</i> , <i>Antho dichotoma</i> , <i>Hymedesmia coriacea</i> , <i>Theca muricata</i> and for other <i>Porifera</i> indent. where otherwise useful information was available. This valuable database has applications for future modelling efforts (addition of faunal components to coupled biogeochemical models) and scientific research.
Need addressed	Scientists need a better understanding of the connections between physical parameters and biological characteristics to support sustainable management in the North Atlantic Ocean. One such key connection is linking metabolic activity and biomass of DWSs and CWCs to the supply of organic matter sources from the water column, something that was hitherto challenging due to the lack of a coherent database of CWC and DWS physiology.
Approach	An extensive literature review of 95 papers (31 general publications; 47 specific to ecophysiology of scleractinian CWCs; 4 papers refer to physiological research with other invertebrates species; 18 dealing with DWS) has been conducted by ATLAS researchers. All existing publications on this topic have been compiled into an excel inventory, and data (533 entries) from the publications have been standardised and stored in databases, transforming the vast knowledge into a more user-friendly format.
Target audience	Scientists, researchers, and academics within and beyond ATLAS who can use the results to further global understanding of ocean circulation and deep ocean ecosystems.
Knowledge Transfer	Science to science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chapter in book: Orejas C., Taviani M., Ambroso S., Andreou V., Bilan M., Bo M., Brodke S., Buñ-Mortensen P., Cordes E., Dominguez-Carrio C., Ferrer-Pagó B., Goñimbo A., Gorr A., J. Grinyó, Gutiérrez-Zárate C., Henige S., Jiménez C., Larsson A., L. Lartaud S., Lunden J., Maier C., Maier S. R., Movilla J., Murray F., Peru E., Purser A., Rakka M., Reynaud S., Roberts JM., Sales P., Strömberg, Thomsen L., van Oevelen D., Vargas A., Carneiro Silva M (2019) Cold-water corals in aquatic advances and challenges. A focus on the Mediterranean. In <i>Mediterranean Cold-Water Corals: Past, Present and Future. Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral</i>. Springer. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-91608-8 Presentations at conferences and workshops: ICES Annual Science Conference, Gothenburg (Sweden), September 2019; ATLAS Science Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), March 2017; ANFORE WS, Lecce (Italy), May 2018.

Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publication: 1 Citation 369 downloads Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 300+ Longer term impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	ATLAS has compiled a substantial body of literature on CWC and DWS ecophysiology and physiology, standardised a number of processes and created a database, the first coherent and standardised database of its kind. The literature review and database are useful tools for researchers working on deep-sea ecology. The database, which includes values on food capture and ingestion, respiration, dissolved and particulate organic carbon, mucus excretion and calcification rate/growth rate, will be useful for comparing novel results with those previously obtained and placing newly obtained results in the context of the existing data.
Next steps	The database will be published and made accessible to all researchers interested in CWC and DWS ecophysiology and physiology. ATLAS researchers are planning to apply this information to design new experiments, leading to further knowledge creation in addition to collaborating with other researchers and feeding this comprehensive new knowledge into models for predicting shifts in deep-water ecosystems.
Contacts and contributors	Covadonga Orejas (IEO), Evert De Froot (NIOZ), Dick van Oevelen (NIOZ) ATLAS Partners: IEO, NIOZ
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2XAFVKL Other ATLAS Deliverable 2.1: Compilation of existing physiological data on CWCs to different conditions of food supply and oceanographic change scenarios zenodo.org/record/3218988#.Wojcasi-uk

Output study 2.2	New approach to identify the key environmental parameters that control cold-water coral ecosystem performance
Description	As "ecosystem engineers", cold-water corals (CWCs) build reefs that are unique biodiversity hotspots in the deep sea. They are considered to be Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) that provide important ecosystem services. The fate of CWCs amidst ongoing global change is difficult to assess as there are limited data on factors that could have a potential negative impact. Therefore, ATLAS developed a new approach, utilising geological data documenting past CWC ecosystem shifts, and correlated them with palaeoceanographic data describing past environmental changes. The results revealed that CWC ecosystem disappearance and reappearance in the North Atlantic Ocean during glacial to warm phase transitions is mostly likely linked to changes in either food supply or bottom water oxygenation, rather than temperature. Changes in these key factors could push CWCs beyond their critical tipping points, possibly triggering their demise, as well as that of the surrounding ecosystem. The outcome improves the prediction of the fate of CWCs and their functions under global change.
Need addressed	To assess the current state accurately, and to predict the future fate of CWCs under changing climates, scientists need a better understanding of the past. Therefore, new approaches to use information from the past are needed to understand past environmental changes and CWC response to climate change. The ability to understand and predict future changes will support sustainable management in the North Atlantic Ocean.

Approach	Using sediment-based approaches, the vitality of CWCs was traced through time at eight case studies in the North Atlantic Ocean. The chemical composition of calcite shells of benthic foraminifera were used as a proxy to infer bottom temperature, salinities, pH, and bottom water provenance. Accumulation rates were used to provide information on food supply and productivity, while grain-size analysis was used to reconstruct hydrodynamic conditions at the seabed.
Target audience	Scientists, researchers, academics, within and beyond ATLAS, who can use the approach to further global understanding of CWC ecosystems.
Knowledge transfer	Science to science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publication: Hebbin D, da Costa Portinho-Ramos R, Wienberg C, and Titschack J (2019) The fate of cold-water corals in a changing world: a geological perspective. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i>, 6, doi:10.3389/fmars.2019.00119 Presentations at conference and workshops: International Conference on Palaeoceanography, Sydney (Australia), September 2019; ATLAS General Assembly, Mallorca (Spain), April 2019. Data available on PANGAEA for exploitation doi:pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.908558
Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication: >2,600 views 4 Citations Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 50 to 100 scientists Longer term impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	Combining several palaeoceanographic and sediment-based approaches, the conditions controlling the growth and distribution of CWCs in the past have been evaluated. This knowledge has great capacity to improve the modelling/prediction of the fate of cold-water corals and their ecosystem functions under future global change.
Next steps	This work represents an additional key approach for assessing the sensitivity of deep-sea organisms to global change, and is of great importance for other scientists active in this field. Deepening this work further, the next step would be to use this novel approach not only to differentiate between coral absence and presence, but to define the optimum conditions for their performance, which could guide the selection of areas where these species should be protected. This approach could also be applied to other deep-sea organisms.
Contact and contributors	Dierk Hebbin (MADUM - UMIH) ATLAS Partners: UMIH
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2VPRY8O

Output study 2.3	Using eDNA and quantitative PCR to assess biodiversity in the open ocean
Description	Observing and sampling deep-sea species pose considerable challenges, such as high costs, lack of opportunity, and difficulties in sampling without causing damage. Addressing the need for new approaches to investigate species/population connectivity in the deep sea, a species-specific, probe-based quantitative PCR (qPCR) assay for detection of target DNA has been developed by ATLAS researchers. Results show that eDNA can be used as a sensitive detection method in the open ocean. With further development, the method has several applications for conservation biology as a non-invasive, rapid and relatively inexpensive tool for monitoring species where traditional surveying methods are not feasible.
Need addressed	Scientists need new tools and approaches to assess biodiversity in the deep sea and open ocean, particularly for those areas that are of conservation concern and/or are difficult to visually observe. Modern molecular techniques (eDNA assays) offer a powerful tool for detecting and assessing the spatial and temporal distribution of target species. Addressing several needs, eDNA assays offer a low-cost alternative to invasive sampling techniques and time-consuming visual surveys.
Approach	To assess the capability of using eDNA to detect transient pelagic marine animals, a species-specific probe-based qPCR assay for detection of target DNA assay was developed, followed by a pilot study to evaluate the capability of this method to determine the presence of the target organism in the field. The assay was developed for the Chilean devil ray, <i>Mobula tarapacana</i> (IUCN Red Listed as Vulnerable species). Seawater samples taken at seamounts around the Azores were tested to determine the suitability of this approach for detecting the target species. The assay successfully detected <i>M. tarapacana</i> at four out of five seamount sampling opportunities where the species was observed.
Target audience	Scientists, researchers, academics, within and beyond ATLAS, who can use the results to increase future utility of eDNA assays as a sensitive tool to detect and assess spatial and temporal distribution of target species.
Knowledge transfer	Science to science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publication: Gargan LM, Moralo T, Pham CK, Finauril JA, Carlsón JEL, Carlsón J (2017) Development of a sensitive detection method to survey pelagic biodiversity using eDNA and quantitative PCR: a case study of devil ray at seamounts. <i>Marine Biology</i> 164, doi.org/10.1007/s00227-017-2941-x Presentations at conference and workshops: UK Environmental DNA Working Group Meeting, Bangor, Wales (UK) September 2015; The International Society for Fish Biology (FSB) Symposium, Bangor, Wales (UK), July 2016.
Impact	Initial measures of impact (June 2020): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication: 1,200 Access 8 Citations Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 300-500 scientists Longer term impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	ATLAS researchers developed a sensitive detection method to survey pelagic biodiversity using eDNA and quantitative PCR. They found that eDNA can be used as a sensitive detection method in the open water and can effectively detect biodiversity hotspots and areas of conservation such as seamounts. The tool has the potential to delineate the spatial and temporal distribution of so far poorly understood species. Combined with visual observations data and presence/absence data based on eDNA, this new method would be an essential precursor to establishing modelling approaches to improve our capabilities to identify important seamounts for conservation and our knowledge of the distribution of <i>M. tarapacana</i> both in the Azores and globally.

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 2: IMPROVE

Next steps	ATLAS researchers are committed to progressing this work through collaborations with other researchers in the field. The next steps include investigating how degradation and transport of eDNA impacts its use for inferring species presence in the open ocean environments and expanding this pilot to other species and regions. Furthermore, combining these results with modelling approaches would improve capabilities to identify important areas for conservation. Developing this work further, temporal and spatial sampling should be extended in order to delineate the distribution of this species and inform conservation management decisions. This approach could be adapted for other oceanic species that are of conservation concern by developing, testing and deploying other species-specific assays.
Contact and contributors	Laura Gargan (UCD - Area 52 research group) ATLAS Partners: UCD, IMAR, UAZ
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2KAVFXL

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 2: IMPROVE

TOGETHER, WE CAN ENSURE THE ATLANTIC OCEAN IS THE BEATING HEART OF OUR WORLD FOR GENERATIONS YET TO COME.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

OBJECTIVE 3 Transform
New data, tools and understanding into effective ocean governance

ATLAS transformed new data, tools and understanding into robust ocean governance in line with an adaptive ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning (MSP) approach to achieve ecosystem preservation, sustainable exploitation, and Blue Growth.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND ACTIVITIES

- 1. Lusó hydrothermal vent field declared as Marine Protected Area:** The Lusó hydrothermal vent field was discovered during the Blue Azores Expedition in 2018, in which ATLAS led Remotely Operated Vehicle operations. In September 2019, the Regional Government of the Azores declared the Lusó hydrothermal vent field a Marine Protected Area (Portaria no. 482/2019), based on the ATLAS findings. This transformation of ATLAS research into policy will ensure deep-sea ecosystems in the Azores are preserved and can be incorporated into plans for sustainable exploitation.
More information: bit.ly/3cFmFR | **Contact:** Teimo Morato, IMAR-UAZ
- 2. ATLAS policy briefs:** ATLAS produced three policy briefs outlining key policy messages from the project and circulated these briefs at relevant intergovernmental events. The three briefs highlight: (i) the need to recognise connectivity and climate change within Marine Protected Area network design, (ii) the utility of economic valuations to highlight the importance of marine ecosystem services, allowing decision makers to draw comparisons with the value of marketed marine products, and (iii) the challenges and potential for collaboration across Blue Growth sectors to enhance synergies and avoid conflicts as a key component of marine spatial planning.
More information: bit.ly/2kT90QS | bit.ly/3ggYNST | bit.ly/2kVAVIT | **see output study 3.2** | **Contact:** Rob Tinch, Iodine | Philip Turner, David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd
- 3. ATLAS Science-Policy Panels:** Three ATLAS Science-Policy panels were held in Brussels, Belgium (March 2017, May 2019) and Ottawa, Canada (May 2018). These events included presentations from ATLAS researchers, discussions on challenges and opportunities, and highlighted the relevance of ATLAS research to specific European policies such as the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive. These events facilitated the direct delivery of ATLAS research results to senior policy makers at international level.
More information: bit.ly/2VUlvv7 | **Contact:** David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd | Murray Roberts, UEDIN
- 4. ATLAS GeoNode marine data visualisation tool:** ATLAS developed an open-access geospatial data repository and visualisation tool using the open-source geospatial content management system (GeoNode) developed by OSGeo. The ATLAS GeoNode allows users to share, visualise and download ATLAS project data and other relevant data layers (e.g. from EMODnet). The repository facilitates the collaborative use of geospatial data and the creation of interactive maps as well as the transfer of ATLAS data and scientific outputs to wider stakeholders in industry and policy.
More information: bit.ly/3c0mAS | **Contact:** Kate Larkin, Tim Collier, Seascope Belgium
- 5. Contribution to the European Commission's Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) by approaching the future assessment of Good Environmental Status (GES) in the deep sea:** ATLAS partners have analysed the definition of GES as well as its descriptors, criteria and indicators, and conducted an initial assessment of GES in the deep sea at nine ATLAS case study sites in European waters. Considering characteristics specific to the deep-sea realm, the current state of the scientific knowledge and current and future threats, ATLAS has proposed a new definition and indicators for GES in the deep sea, and made recommendations to inform future revisions of the MSFD for GES assessments in European waters and in areas beyond national jurisdiction.
More information: Kazanidis et al. (accepted) | Orjés et al. (in review) | **see output study 2.1** | **Contact:** Covadonga Orjés, EIO | Georgios Kazanidis, UEDIN
- 6. Input to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) regional workshop on Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas (EBSAs) in the North-East Atlantic Ocean:** ATLAS contributed to the workshop and report organised by the Secretariat of the CBD (Stockholm, Sweden, September 2019). The data provided by ATLAS contributed to the description of six features that meet the EBSA criteria: (i) The Gulf of Cadiz, (ii) Tropic Seamount, (iii) North Azores Plateau, (iv) Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone, (v) Southern Reykjanes Ridge and (vi) the Hutton and Rockall Banks and Basin. This work supports the implementation of the EBSA process and informs future management measures in the deep sea.
More information: cbd.int/meetings/EBSA-WS-2019-01 | **see output study 3.3** | **Contact:** Christopher Barrio Projan, David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd | Lea-Anne Henry, Murray Roberts, UEDIN
- 7. Work with the International Seabed Authority (ISA):** The ATLAS team made a submission to the ISA regarding draft regulations on Exploitation of Mineral Resources in the Area (beyond national jurisdictions). The submission addressed two questions from the ISA Council and highlighted the importance of open access data, data sharing, particularly with industry, and cumulative impact of climate change on the resilience of the marine environment. ATLAS results on AMOC, food web dynamics and vulnerability of Marine Protected Areas to changes in the ocean) were also used in the supporting materials at an ISA workshop and data report (November 2019).
More information: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2020144 | **Contact:** Rachel Boschen-Rosa, David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd
- 8. Submission to the UK Government's Sustainable Seas Inquiry:** The UK Government's Sustainable Seas Inquiry (April 2018) examined how ocean life can be protected from ocean acidification, overfishing, resource extraction and pollution. The ATLAS submission to the inquiry was cited eight times in the resulting Environmental Audit Committee Report and used to highlight the potential impact of deep-sea mining and as evidence for the threat of climate change. Since the inquiry, the UK Government has reaffirmed its commitment to the UN Framework

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

More information: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1544234 | Contact: Rachel Boschen-Rosa, David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd

9. Contributions to the United Nations negotiations on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biodiversity: ATLAS has contributed to the development of an International Legally Binding Instrument (ILBI) on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biodiversity in areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (BNJ) by the UN. ATLAS partners participated in the four Preparatory Committee sessions (March 2016, August 2016, March 2017, July 2017). In addition, the team contributed an article that provided information on the process, highlighted some of the features of the putative instrument under discussion, and outlined some of the issues at play in the process for regional groupings of states, countries with significant maritime interests and non-governmental representatives. The team also attended the Intergovernmental Conference (September 2018, March 2019, August 2019), on the development of an ILBI for BNJ. In 2019, ATLAS researchers ran a project examining how BNJ stakeholders perceived the importance of science to the negotiations. These contributions have ensured both that ATLAS results are shared in a timely manner with delegations as they discuss and develop policy and that the significance of scientific input is better understood. **More information:** bit.ly/3b5meh6 | **Contact:** Ronan Long, WMU | David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd | Christine Gaebel, J Murray Roberts UEDIN

10. Contributions to the United Nations' Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) special report on the ocean and cryosphere in a changing climate: Providing guidance and recommendations on ocean governance and conservation to global policy makers, ATLAS research and results on ocean acidification and sea level modeling were included in the IPCC's latest report on Changing Oceans, Marine Ecosystems, and Dependent Communities (2019). **More information:** bit.ly/2K9690V | **Contact:** Alan Fox, Sebastian Hennige, J Murray Roberts, UEDIN | Jake Rice (ATLAS Advisory Board Chair), DFO

11. Contributions to the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) database: ATLAS has provided unequivocal evidence for several new VME habitats at Formigas and Ormonde seamounts and Gazu Mud volcano (ATLAS case study 7). These new VME habitat records have been added to the ICES VME database which is used to provide scientifically robust advice on the distribution of VMEs and to guide possible management solutions to protect VMEs. **More information:** bit.ly/2XxY2YU | **Contact:** Covadonga Orejas, IEO

OUTPUT STUDIES

Output study 3.1	Approaching the assessment of Good Environmental Status in the deep sea
Description	The suitability of the definition, descriptors, criteria and indicators applied to determine Good Environmental Status (GES) in the deep sea has been assessed. Significant gaps were found in the current GES assessment, since they failed to account for specific deep-sea characteristics. Taking these into consideration, ATLAS partners have proposed a new definition of GES for the deep sea that considers the current state of scientific knowledge and understanding of present and future threats. ATLAS defines GES in the deep sea to mean that the extraction of living marine resources is occurring at sustainable levels and the extraction of non-living resources does not produce significant adverse impacts that cause serious harm in the whole ecosystem, i.e. levels of extraction ensure continued delivery of goods and services for future generations. In particular, deep-sea GES is achieved when habitat-forming species are in 'good' condition, defined by acting as biodiversity hotspots and ensuring the continued ecosystem functionality, including all associated benthic, suprabenthic and demersal components. Areas dominated by soft sediments (e.g. the abyssal plains) maintain biodiversity at a level that ensures persistence of functional groups and thus ecosystem function, impacts on the seabed and their effects on benthos and fish (commercial and non-commercial species) do not increase the risk of altered or lost ecosystem functioning, ensuring the sustainable use of deep-sea resources and the continued resilience of ecosystems in the face of a changing climate.
Need addressed	There is a clear need for robust ocean governance, based on the best and latest data, tools, and understanding of the ocean at large. The current methodology to define and describe Good Environmental Status (GES) needs to be adapted for the specific characteristics of the deep sea. ATLAS investigated a new definition of GES for the deep sea.
Approach	The Nested Environmental Status Assessment Tool (NEAT), developed within the European DEVOTES project, was evaluated as an appropriate tool to assess the environmental status of the deep sea. NEAT was applied to nine European deep-sea case study areas to identify indicators that are suitable for the deep sea due to their intrinsic characteristics, as well as to the level of available information (e.g. density of megabenthic structuring species as cold-water corals). Additional indicators, not included in the NEAT tool, were added to include the ECS MSFD descriptors. An extensive literature review was conducted to facilitate the selection of threshold values for each GES indicator. The results highlighted the scarcity of deep-sea data currently available, even in 'well-studied' case study areas and that the selection of indicators, thresholds and spatial scale, habitats and ecosystem components, can have a significant impact on the NEAT results.
Target audience	International organisations (e.g. OECD, FAO, UN), policy makers, EU and member state policy makers, managers, scientists, researchers, academics.

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orejas C, Kenchington E, Rice J, Kazanidis G, Pallares A, Johnson D, Gianri M, Danovaro R, Roberts JM (in review) <i>Marine Policy</i> Kazanidis G, Orejas C, Borja A, Kenchington E, Henry L-A, Callery O, Carrero-Silva M, Egido-Oliver H, Giacomello E, Grellet A, Menot L, Morato T, Ragnarsson SA, Rueda JL, Stirling D, Stratmann T, van Oevelen D, Pallares A, Johnson D, Roberts JM (accepted in <i>Ecological Indicators</i>) Presentations at conference and workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing European Marine Policies in the deep waters of the North Atlantic. Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland webinar youtube.com/watch?v=HYvG6H8RVU8&t=25 International Council for the Exploration of the Sea Working Group on Fisheries Benthic Impacts and Trade-Offs (ICES WGFBI), Ancona (Italy), September 2019 International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) - Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO) Joint Working Group on Deep-water Ecology (WGDEC), Copenhagen (Denmark), March 2017; Dartmouth (Canada), March 2018; Malorca (Spain), June 2019 IDEM project meeting, Rome (Italy), March 2019. Academic visit and presentation at the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, Ispra (Italy) 2019 Scotland's International Marine Conference, Glasgow (UK), February 2019 Implementation of the MSFD to the Deep Mediterranean Sea workshop, University of Malta, Msida (Malta), 2018 Data available on PANGAEA for exploitation: from June 2020 <p>Science to policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentations at conference and workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATLAS Science-Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), May 2019 ICES/NAFO WGDEC, Copenhagen (Denmark), March 2017; Dartmouth (Canada), March 2018; Malorca (Spain), June 2019 European Commission's Joint Research Centre, March 2019 Contribution to ICES, 2017. ICES/NAFO WGDEC. bit.ly/3d2PJD Contribution to ICES, 2019. Annex 4 within 2018 Report of the Working Group on Fisheries Benthic Impact and Tradeoffs (WGFBI). bit.ly/3anWwQ Contributed, through consultations, to the Marine Strategy Coordination Group_22-2018-06 document (Good environmental status for MSFD Descriptor 1 (seabed habitats) and Descriptor 6 (sea-floor integrity) prepared by the European Commission's Directorate-general for Environment. bit.ly/2xT7yJd) <p>Science to industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presented at Ocean Business 2019, Southampton (UK), April 2019 <p>Science to industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Article in ATLAS Project Newsletter, Issue 7, February 2020. bit.ly/3fVUGW
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 360 + scientists Newsletter readers: 200 + Longer term impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to regional governance policies through recommendations made from ICES Contribution to revisions of the European Commission's Marine Strategy Frameworks Contribution to the deliberations surrounding the negotiation of the United Nations Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction Treaty regulation Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

Take home message	ATLAS proposes a new assessment, including a new definition of GES, which better addresses the specific characteristics of the deep sea, as well as a set of the most suitable indicators (24 in total) and threshold values for each indicator to appropriately assess GES in the deep sea. The results and recommendations proposed by ATLAS for future GES assessments have important implications for regulatory bodies and the development of policy tools. They should be used to inform future revisions of the European Commission's MSFD and as a basis for the assessment of the deep sea in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs).
Next steps	This work will facilitate identification and establishment of future research priorities and address challenges in the assessment of deep-sea environmental status. To inform policy, next steps should be to present this work to the European Commission, Regional Sea Conventions (OSPAR), International Council for the Exploration of the Sea and the United Nations. ATLAS is committed to engaging with regional and international organisations to achieve this.
Contacts and contributors	Covadonga Orejas (IEO), Georgios Kazanidis (UEDIN) ATLAS Partners: IEO, UEDIN, DFO, NUIO, IMAR-UAZ, MFR, Seascope Consultants Ltd, UK, IREMER, MSL, INOCE, UNCW, Other contributors: AZTI, Utrecht University, European Commission Joint Research Centre, Deep Sea Conservation Coalition, Center for Marine Science, Polytechnic University of Marche, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn Naples.
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2XAVFKL
Output study 3.2	Current deep-sea Area-Based Management Tools are unprepared for climate change
Description	The functionality of several Area-Based Management Tools (ABMTs) designed to protect biodiversity in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (more than 200 nautical miles) in the North Atlantic Ocean have been assessed. ATLAS partners have found spatial and temporal scale issues with current climate models and identified knowledge gaps. Currently, ABMTs are being applied on the basis of contemporary environmental conditions and habitat distribution. However, climate change and geographic shifts in environmental gradients will likely affect individual species, habitat integrity and representativeness. Different ecosystem components will react/respond differently to individual environmental stressors, and to the cumulative effects of a changing environment driven by climate change. Therefore, it is critically important to understand if, and when, these ecological features may change in response to climate change, potentially reducing or negating the value of ABMTs and their associated management systems. The results have important implications for future policy plans and decisions designed to protect biodiversity in the deep ocean.
Need Addressed	To create fit-for-purpose, adaptive, ecosystem-based maritime spatial plans, there is a need to know how well current Marine Protected Area network designs work, and recognise weaknesses that can be addressed in future plans.
Approach	A Pressure-State-Response (PSR) framework was used to (i) identify and characterise pressures on ABMTs, (ii) characterise the ecological / biological state of ABMTs and predict shifts in response to pressures and, (iii) to identify potential responses and measures to fill gaps identified. Three ABMTs were assessed: 1) OSPAR Marine Protected Areas, 2) Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs), and 3) Regional Fisheries Management Organisations' (RFMOs) closures to protect Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). They were assessed for a 20-to-50-year timeframe, using a stepwise methodology based on five key variables, building on available technical and scientific information.

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

Approach	The five variables assessed showed differing levels of uncertainty with respect to impacts on key taxa under climate change projections. With the exception of one EBSA, all of the conservation targets in all of the current MPAs, EBSAs and areas closed to fishing to protect VMEs may be impacted by changes in at least one of the five climate change oceanographic variables before 2050.
Target audience	International organisations (e.g. CBD, FAO, OSPAR, NAFO, NEAFC), policy makers, EU and member state policy makers, managers, scientists, researchers, academics.
Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publication: Johnson D, Ferreira MA, Kenchington E (2018) Climate change is likely to severely limit the effectiveness of deep-sea ABMTs in the North Atlantic. <i>Marine Policy</i>, 87, 111-122. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.09.034 Presentations at conference and workshops: IUCN experts' meetings, Gland and Paris (France), October 2018; OSPAR IGC-MPA, Marstrand (Sweden), October 2018; CBD COP14, Sharm El-Sheikh (Egypt), November 2018; FAO GEF Deep Sea Project meeting, Reunion (France), January 2019; IGC 12 UN New York (USA), March 2019; IODRI expert meeting, Paris (France), April 2019; DOSI expert workshop, San Diego (USA), June 2019; European Aquarium Congress, Nautica (France), October 2019. <p>Science to policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part of ATLAS Policy Brief presented to the UN Intergovernmental Conference, New York (USA), March 2019 Presented at ATLAS Science-Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), May 2019 Presented at OSPAR Intersectoral Correspondence Group on MPAs, Sweden, October 2019 <p>Science to industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presented at Ocean Business 2019, Southampton (UK), April 2019 <p>Science to industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Article in ATLAS Project Newsletter, issue 6, August 2019. bit.ly/3FvGu5W
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications: > 170 reads 17 Citations Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 100 + Newsletter readers: 200 + Policy audience at conferences and workshops: 150 + <p>Longer term impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This work has informed planning considerations by the OSPAR Commission and informal meetings of projects, workshops and conferences considering biodiversity protection in the deep-sea (see previous list above). Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	There is a need for more complete impact assessments, and further research including the impact of additional variables and more precise and reliable spatial and temporal models. Conservation targets for highly mobile species can likely be met by redesigning ABMTs, and for sessile/low mobility species, there are a number of mitigation options to support short-term conservation efforts.
Next steps	Detailed work on ABMTs on a case-by-case basis could inform future conservation priorities. A specific focus for future studies could be on ecosystem tipping points. ATLAS is committed to share this work with policy makers and international organisations (e.g. CBD, FAO, OSPAR, NAFO, NEAFC) to inform future impact assessments and research to achieve appropriate conservation targets.
Contact and contributors	David Johnson (Seascope Consultants Ltd) ATLAS Partners: Seascope Consultants Ltd, DFO
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2X7NsUR

Output study 3.3	New evidence to support the protection of deep-sea sponge ecosystems at Tropic Seamount
Description	<p>ATLAS partners have developed new information and data to support robust ocean governance by contributing to data describing six features that meet the Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Areas (EBSAs) criteria, including Tropic Seamount.</p> <p>With the support of new models and habitat suitability maps, ATLAS discovered extensive monospecific grounds of the hexactinellid sponge <i>Polyspongia amadou</i> at Tropic Seamount, a potential Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME), located in an Area Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) in the subtropical North Atlantic. <i>P. amadou</i>, the only member of its genus in the Atlantic Ocean, is a large, fan-shaped phoronematid sponge that reaches up to 35 cm in height. Even though it is a habitat-forming VME indicator species, its occurrence was poorly understood. An ensemble species distribution model and local habitat suitability maps for the sponge in the Atlantic Ocean were produced and tested by direct observation during a subsequent research expedition.</p> <p>The results from this study have implications for spatial management and describing additional VMEs and EBSAs. Working towards a high seas marine protected area network, the results have been used to inform a submission to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) to designate the Tropic Seamount as an EBSA. Designating the seamount as an EBSA is an important first step towards any future sustainable management and protection measures.</p>
Need addressed	To achieve ecosystem preservation and sustainable exploitation, there is an urgent need to transform new data into ocean governance measures. The ability to predict the presence of VMEs will support future measures and guide Blue Growth.
Approach	First, to gather new information and to predict the distribution of this VME indicator sponge on the Tropic Seamount, ATLAS partners created an ensemble habitat suitability map for <i>P. amadou</i> distribution. Three different modelling techniques were used, Maximum Entropy, General Additive Models, and Random Forest, for the purpose of management applications. These models can help fill gaps and create distribution maps in areas where data is not available, thereby providing some guidance (where previously there were none) before any exploitation activities. Increasing spatial coverage beyond the range of Remotely Operated Vehicles and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles surveys in the area, predictive maps are useful tools to inform ongoing high seas management efforts such as maritime spatial planning, environmental impact assessments, conservation of biogeographically unique provinces, and UN negotiations of a new treaty to protect biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction (BNJ). For example, the information generated from this research contributed to scientific information submitted to describe an EBSA to the CBD.
Target audience	International organisations, policy makers, EU and member state policymakers, managers, scientists, researchers, academics.
Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publication: Ramiro-Sánchez B, González-Irujo JM, Henry L-A, Casand J, Yeo I, Xavier JS, Carreiro-Silva H, Sampola I, Spearman J, Victoreo L, Messing C G, Kazandis G, Roberts JM, Merton B (2019) Characterization and Mapping of a Deep-Sea Sponge Ground on the Tropic Seamount (Northwest Tropical Atlantic): Implications for Spatial Management in the High Seas. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> 6, 278. doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00278 <p>Science to policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CBD Regional Workshop EBSAs in the North East Atlantic, Stockholm (Sweden), September 2019 ATLAS Science-Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), May 2019 Submission of scientific information to Describe Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas to Convention on Biological Diversity. cdb.int/meetings/EBSA-WS-2019-01 October 2019

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFORM

Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to society</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media coverage: Spanish media EFE, VERDE (October 2019) bit.ly/2XSVuSR A.A.S Science Magazine (September 2019) bit.ly/3ATXN1Q
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication: >3,450 views 3 Citations Policy audience at meetings and workshops: 100 + Media reach: 500 + <p>Longer term impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of Tropic Seamount in the CBD EBSA repository Contribution to cross-sectoral management and ocean governance measures for conservation and sustainable use of deep-sea biodiversity Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	ATLAS researchers have established substantial new knowledge on the distribution of sponges, their preferred conditions (water depth and current speed), and toward understanding the environmental drivers and biogeography of species in the Atlantic Ocean. This research has implications for future spatial management and describing vulnerable marine ecosystems. The results generated contributed to scientific information submitted to the CBD, supporting the description of Tropic Seamount as an EBSA, part of a contribution to addressing biodiversity conservation in Areas Beyond National Jurisdictions.
Next steps	Designating the seamount as an EBSA is the first step. In the future, this could help set spatial planning measures in situ in case of exploitation. From a research perspective, the next steps to continue this work would be community analyses of the vertical distribution of other VMEs observed on the seamount. The methods can be applied and used by others to further increase spatial coverage and further increase knowledge and understanding of VMEs, to improve policy tools and spatial planning in marine exploitation, and ultimately leading to better ocean governance.
Contact and contributors	Berta Ramiro-Sanchez, Lea-Anne Henry (UEDIN) ATLAS Partners: UEDIN, IMAR-UAZ, Seascope Consultants Ltd
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2RZOW7N

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4 DEVELOP

OBJECTIVE 4 Develop

And scenario-test science-led, cost-effective adaptive management strategies that stimulate Blue Growth

ATLAS developed and scenario-tested science-led, cost-effective adaptive management strategies for sustainable use of living and non-living resources that stimulate Blue Growth.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4 DEVELOP

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND ACTIVITIES

- Area-based resource management plans for ATLAS case studies:** ATLAS has assessed the science base available to support the development of regional area-based management plans in the North Atlantic Ocean. Existing information about ecosystem components, human activities and governance have been collated for each ATLAS case study area. Environmental risk assessments have been conducted for each case study to provide a baseline for planning. Blue Growth scenarios were tested using systematic conservation planning tools, MarxAN and InPrestis, to help promote global, regional and local conservation targets but also to determine the optimal locations for Blue Growth activities while minimising impacts. These results will contribute to the implementation of the Integrated Maritime Policy (EC COM(2017) 575).
More information: bit.ly/2VcufrU | **Contact:** Anthony Grehan, NUI Galway
- Blue Growth scenarios tested at ATLAS case studies:** A range of different Blue Growth scenarios have been identified and tested across ATLAS case studies. Blue Growth scenarios for: oil and gas exploration/exploitation, deep-sea mining, expansion of Arctic fisheries, EU Natura 2000 sites (designated sites protected under the Birds and Habitats Directive), tidal energy, ecotourism and carbon sequestration have been tested at relevant ATLAS case study sites. The potential impact of developing these activities on the environment, and for already existing activities in the case studies, was assessed to inform managers of potential Blue Growth scenarios about user conflicts and to provide examples where governance needs to be strengthened to deliver robust area-based management.
More information: ATLAS Deliverable 6.3 (see p61) | **Contact:** Anthony Grehan, NUI Galway
- Novel Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) decision support protocol:** ATLAS has developed a streamlined workflow to facilitate the implementation of the 'Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Area' (MESMA) generic planning framework (developed under the EU Framework Programme 7 project - MESMA) and to test Blue Growth scenarios across ATLAS case studies. The workflow supports the production and presentation of transparent information to stakeholders and enables greater connectivity and interoperability.
More information: ATLAS Deliverable 6.3 (see p61) | see output study 4.1 | **Contact:** Oisín Callery, Anthony Grehan, NUI Galway
- Identification of Blue Growth industry drivers:** ATLAS partners have gained novel insights into business drivers, priorities and challenges facing Blue Economy sectors (i.e. biotechnology, oil and gas, renewable energy, shipping, tourism, fisheries, offshore aquaculture and deep seabed mining) through a series of interviews and questionnaires. Between now and 2030, important business drivers for Blue Growth sectors in the North Atlantic Ocean include: technology development, regulation development and climate change impacts. This work highlighted shared spatial challenges across several Blue Growth sectors and the need for collective

adaptive management strategies.
More information: D73 bit.ly/2LX202B | Bosch-Rose RE et al (2020) | **Contact:** Rachel Bosch-Rose, Seaspace Consultants Ltd | Matt Gianni, Gianni Consultancy

- Industry data sharing:** Through collaboration among ATLAS researchers and international oil companies Equinor and BP, ATLAS has supported better monitoring efforts at case study sites including Løve Observatory, Norway and West of Shetland. ATLAS organised three international industry workshops (Edinburgh, UK-2016; Poole, UK-2017; Dublin, Ireland-2018) and two questionnaires to facilitate the dissemination of industry-relevant ATLAS innovations. The identified guiding principles for future data sharing are expected to improve business practices and reduce costs. Ensuring stakeholder involvement and use of best available data, through data sharing, this work supports the implementation of the EU Directive on Marine Spatial Planning for sustainable Blue Growth.
More information: ATLAS Deliverables 6.4 (see p61) | **Contact:** Lisa-Anne Henry, UEDIN
- Contribution to the development of NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets:** ATLAS research on the impact of human activities, other than fishing, at ATLAS case study 11 (Flemish Cap - Flemish Pass) has been incorporated into Ecosystem Summary Sheets developed by the Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO). These sheets are part of the NAFO's Roadmap for an ecosystem approach to fisheries, and will be used to inform decision making by both managers and industry in the Northwest Atlantic Ocean in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ).
More information: bit.ly/3a0ag9v (2nd IAFD VWC-USA Report, p.120) | see output study 4.3 | **Contact:** Pablo Durán Muñoz, Mar Sacau, IEO
- Predictive maps for future habitat suitability:** ATLAS partners have modified and developed predictive maps of habitat suitability for six cold-water coral and six deep-sea fish species under current conditions and forecast changes under future projected high-emission climate conditions for the whole North Atlantic Ocean. The results forecasted that over 50% of cold-water coral habitat could be at risk, and suitable habitats for commercially important deep-sea fish could shift by up to 100 km northwards. This work has important implications for the designation of effective area-based conservation measures and adaptive management strategies.
More information: bit.ly/36V2WA | see output study 4.2 | **Contact:** Temo Morato, IMAR-UAZ

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4 DEVELOP

OBJECTIVE 4 - DEVELOP | OUTPUT STUDIES

Output study 4.1	Novel Marine Spatial Planning decision support protocol
Description	A novel workflow required to facilitate application to test Blue Growth scenarios in deep-sea areas has been developed by ATLAS partners to inform adaptive management. The workflow supports the implementation of the EU Framework Programme 7 'Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Areas' (MESMA) generic planning framework in ATLAS case studies. The workflow enables greater connectivity and interoperability of marine data, increasing the use and exploitation of available data while also identifying gaps that can be filled by novel modelling approaches. The workflow has been developed using open source R with data visualisation performed using the open source QGIS. This enables transparent presentation of information (and all processing steps) to stakeholders (e.g. mapped cumulative impact scores for ATLAS case studies). The workflow will assist marine spatial planning and the delivery of ecosystem-based management as well as highlighting lacunae and issues to be addressed by ocean governance.
Need Addressed	Maritime Spatial Planning in the offshore and deep-sea areas is still in its infancy. To ensure that Blue Growth can take place while protecting biodiversity, a robust MSP framework is required to deliver holistic, ecosystem-based management in the ocean. Such a framework should support adaptive management to ensure sustainable use of living and non-living resources as new Blue Growth opportunities present themselves. To support the development of such plans and to facilitate testing, new methods and tools are needed to integrate new data sources (e.g. Global Fishing Watch data) into the MSP framework.
Approach	The 'Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Area' (MESMA) generic planning framework includes a series of steps for each spatially managed area including data collection (ecosystem components, human activities, governance), identification of indicators, risk analysis and state assessment, and adaptive management evaluation. The workflow was developed: i) to support implementation of MESMA in the Atlantic Ocean, which allows compilation of the relevant data layers (drawn from the ATLAS data repository), easily compiling data from different sources with different resolutions and spatial scales ii) to enable practitioners with little programming knowledge to perform cumulative effects assessments using pre-packaged R scripts iii) to produce raster outputs that can be inputted into QGIS for data visualisation and mapping, and into MarxAN or similar, for testing management scenarios including systematic conservation planning. See also: zenodo.org/record/3761218#.21QW058ZNNI
Target audience	International policy advisory organisations (e.g. JNCC, ICES), EU and member state policymakers, managers, offshore operators, oil and gas industry, scientists, researchers, academics.
Knowledge transfer	Science to science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kazanidis et al (accepted) Combes et al (in review) Callery et al (in preparation) Presentations at conferences and workshops including ATLAS MSP Webinar, Department of Fisheries and Oceans, March 2020; Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) - Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy Ireland (MaREI) Science Conference, Limerick (Ireland), November 2019; Socio-Economic Marine Research Unit (SEMUR) 10th Annual Economics and Policy Research Symposium, Galway (Ireland), November 2019.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4 DEVELOP

Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentations at conference and workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICES Workshop on EU regulatory area options for VME Protection (WKEUVME), online, May 2020. bit.ly/228yruP Irish MPA Expert Advisory Group meetings, Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government. Multiple meetings held in Dublin (Ireland) and online, December 2019, February, April 2020 ICES Stakeholder Workshop to Disseminate the ICES Deep-Sea Access Regulation: Technical Service, and Scope the Required Steps for Regulatory Purposes (WREG), Copenhagen (Denmark), October 2019 ICES Workshop on Tradeoffs Scenarios between the Impact on Seafloor Habitats and Provisions of catch/Value (WKTRADE2), Copenhagen (Denmark), September 2019 ICES Working Group on Deep-Sea Ecology (WGDEC), Copenhagen (Denmark), June 2018; Mallorca (Spain), June 2019 ICES Working Group on Marine Planning and Coastal Zone Management (WGMPCZM), Galway (Ireland), April 2019 ATLAS Symposium on Future Prospects for North Atlantic EBSAs, VMEs and MPAs, WCMC, Montreal (Canada), May 2018 Perspectives on Area-Based Management: Tools for ABNJ, Trans-Atlantic Assessment and Deep-water Ecosystem-based Spatial Management Plan International Workshop, Nausicaa, Bologne-sur-Mer (France), June 2018 Contribution to reports: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICES, 2019. WKTRADE2. bit.ly/2VDWdWC ICES, 2019. WKEUVME. bit.ly/3KZDXIA ICES, 2019. WREG. bit.ly/351r3H ICES, 2020. WGMPCZM (outputs from 2019 meeting). bit.ly/36Fexw8 Irish MPA expert advisory group, 2020. Expanding Ireland's Marine Protected Area Network report (due in July 2020) Science to industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ocean Business ATLAS side event, Southampton (UK), April 2019 ATLAS/MaREI/Irish Offshore Operators Association joint industry workshop: 'Supporting Blue Growth' (Dublin (Ireland), December 2019) Science to society <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Article in ATLAS Project Newsletter, Issue 7, February 2020. bit.ly/37GvGwG
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 150+ scientists Newsletter readers: 200+ Policy audience at conferences and workshops: 150+ Industry audience at conferences and workshops: 50+ <p>Longer term impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to national initiatives to establish Marine Protected Areas Contribution to regional governance policies through recommendations made from ICES Contribution to the deliberations surrounding the negotiation of the United Nations Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction treaty regulation
Take home message	Facilitating Marine Spatial Planning, and the development of adaptive management strategies for the deep sea, a novel workflow/tool has been developed to support the implementation of MESMA and to test Blue Growth scenarios at ATLAS case studies. The tool facilitates the planning process, potentially reduces business costs (i.e. conducting Environmental Impact Assessments) and supports achievement of global, regional and local conservation targets through systematic conservation planning.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4: DEVELOP

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4: DEVELOP

Next steps	The workflow (together with a tool developed in parallel with SFI MaREI) needs to be marketed and disseminated to increase uptake by policy makers and industry. ATLAS partner NUI Galway, and MaREI are committed to disseminating this work and carrying out the next steps, including the development of a web application, online tutorials (training) and workshops on how to use the tool, as well as collaborations with potential practitioners (i.e. local, regional and national planners). Trials with stakeholder groups are also envisaged. The workflow will be dynamic and can be improved as new data and knowledge, e.g. our understanding of species responses to pressures resulting from human activities, become available.
Contacts and contributors	Anthony Graham, Oisín Cattery (NUIG) and MaREI Observation and Operations Spoke (SFI) ATLAS Partners: NUIG, DFO
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2RZOW7N

Output study 4.2	New climate model projects major impacts on coral and commercially important fish habitats in the deep Atlantic due to climate change
Description	Understanding how anticipated climate change will affect deep-sea species distributions, including commercially important fishes, is critically important in developing effective management measures. Addressing the need to understand these shifts, ATLAS partners have modelled and developed predictive maps. These maps display habitat suitability for six cold-water coral and six deep-sea fish species under current conditions, and also forecast changes under projected high-emission climate conditions for the whole North Atlantic Ocean. The results strongly suggest that warming, acidification, and decreasing food availability will compound to significantly reduce the availability of suitable habitats for deep-sea species by 2100. The models forecast a decrease of 28-100% of suitable habitat for cold-water corals, and a shift in suitable habitat for deep-sea fishes of 2.0° - 9.0° towards higher latitudes. This work highlights the importance of identifying and preserving climate refugia. It also has important implications for fisheries management, for conserving and protecting Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs), and for the designation of effective area-based conservation measures, planning and management tools.
Need Addressed	We need adaptive management strategies for sustainable use of living and non-living resources in the deep Atlantic Ocean that stimulate Blue Growth, particularly in response to climate change. Understanding how anticipated climate change will affect deep-sea species distributions, including commercially important fishes, is critically important in developing effective management measures.
Approach	Using the best available species occurrence data, a set of static measures (e.g. depth, slope) and near-bottom dynamic environmental parameters (particulate organic carbon flux to the seabed, near seafloor pH, dissolved oxygen concentration, temperature, and near seafloor argonite and calcite saturation state) that predict suitable habitats under future climate conditions for VME indicator species and deep-sea fish species have been developed. Habitat suitability for six cold-water coral and six deep-sea fish species under present-day (1951-2000) environmental conditions and forecast changes in a severe, high emission future (2081-2100, RCP8.5 scenario) have been modelled for the North Atlantic Ocean.

Target audience	Marine spatial planners, offshore operators, international organisations, policy makers, scientists, researchers, academics.
Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Morato T et al (2020) Climate-induced changes in the suitable habitat of cold-water corals and commercially important deep-sea fishes in the North Atlantic. <i>Global Change Biology</i>. doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14999 Method for other scientists to access and exploit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep-sea species distribution modelling workshop, Montreal (Canada), May 2018. bit.ly/2WYMG3C <p>Science to policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATLAS Science-Policy Panel, Brussels (Belgium), May 2019 Data from this work contributed to the description of features meeting the Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Areas (EBSA) criteria that were presented to the Convention on Biological Diversity (see p52) <p>Science to society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press Release: bit.ly/3D8ClVg
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication: 2 Citations Scientific audience at conferences and workshops: 100 + Media coverage: 1000 + hits (AlphaGalileo) 130 + reached (Altmetric) <p>Longer term impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to future long-term sustainable environmental management and conservation policies, particularly those relating to Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems and Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	ATLAS research has found that the availability of suitable habitat for cold-water corals and deep-sea fish species is expected to significantly decrease by 2100. Environmental niche modelling is a valuable tool for forecasting changes in habitat suitability. This approach can help to integrate climate change considerations as part of area-based management decisions or conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in international areas.
Next steps	ATLAS hopes that the results will be used to enhance international dialogue on basin-scale management. Habitat suitability models are powerful tools to inform such discussions on conservation policy and environmental management. The model presented here can be used as a template and applied to other taxa or in additional regions to resolve changes in distribution and identification of refugia for monitoring purposes.
Contact and contributors	Teimo Morato (MaR-LA2) ATLAS Partners: IMAR-UIAZ, UEDIN, DFO, IEG, NUI Galway, IFREMER, MRFI, Glaxi Consultancy, Seascope Consultants Ltd, SAMS, NIOZ
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2XAVFXL

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4: DEVELOP

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4: DEVELOP

Output study 4.3	Contribution to the development of NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets
Description	Supporting the implementation of ATLAS research in ocean management and blue growth, results from ATLAS case study II, Flemish Cap - Flemish Pass, have been incorporated into NAFO (Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organisation) Ecosystem Summary Sheets (ESS) as part of NAFO's Roadmap for an Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries. The ESS will be presented to the NAFO Commission in September 2020 and are intended to provide a synoptic perspective on the state of NAFO ecosystems and their management regime. ATLAS results (i.e. maps) show the spatial overlap of footprints from human activities, other than fishing. These insights are combined with mapping of other ecosystem components to highlight existing or potential conflicts between users of the NAFO marine space and Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). ATLAS results have contributed to several sections of the ESS including VME status, oil and gas activities and pollution, specifically marine litter. Following the recommendations of the NAFO Working Group on Ecosystem Science and Assessment (WGESA) to the NAFO Scientific Council, protocols for collecting marine litter data for monitoring purposes should be implemented by all contracting parties during groundfish surveys in the NAFO regulatory area. The NAFO ESS's constitute a tool for strategic assessment, advice, and planning for the Northwest part of the Atlantic Ocean in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), supporting the direct implementation of ATLAS research in ocean management and governance.
Need addressed	Organisations governing the use of ocean resources need scenario-tested and science-led adaptive management strategies. Supporting the development of such strategies, ATLAS has developed tools (maps) that identify resource use and highlight existing or potential spatial conflict.
Approach	A Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) framework was applied to produce maps of relevant natural and socio-economic components of the deep-sea ecosystem of the Flemish Cap - Flemish Pass. The maps are useful tools for advising governance measures, particularly in areas of potential spatial conflict, such as the Flemish Pass. For example, at that site, a proposed project for oil and gas development overlaps with the NAFO fisheries area, VMEs, and areas currently closed to bottom fishing to protect cold-water corals and sponges.
Target audience	International organisations (e.g. OECD, FAO, UN, REMO) that can use the information to guide decision making, as well as scientists, researchers, academics, within and beyond ATLAS, with technical expertise that further this research.
Knowledge transfer	<p>Science to science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> García-Alegre et al (2020). Seabed litter distribution in the high-seas of the Flemish Pass area (NW Atlantic). <i>Scientia Marina</i>, 84. doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04945.27A Duran Muñoz et al (2020). Cold-water corals and deep-sea sponges by-catch mitigation: Dealing with groundfish survey data in the management of the northwest Atlantic Ocean high seas fisheries. <i>Marine Policy</i>, 116. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103712 Presentations at conference and workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> World Conference on Marine Biodiversity, Montreal (Canada), May 2018 VI International Symposium on Marine Sciences, Vigo (Spain), June 2018 MAREC-16 International Conference, Vigo (Spain), May 2018 ICES Annual Science Conference, Gothenburg (Sweden), September 2019. ICES CM 2019/O-36 11th and 12th NAFO Working Group on Ecosystem Science and Assessment (WGESA) meetings, Dartmouth (Canada), November 2018, 2019. bit.ly/2YAVSRN; bit.ly/3baagwv

Knowledge transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATLAS MSP Webinar, Department of Fisheries and Oceans, March 2020 NAFO Scientific Council Research Documents: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sacala et al (2020). bit.ly/2S5dWvD Duran Muñoz et al. (2020) Data on VMEs available on PANGAEA and EMODnet for exploitation. doi: doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.91147 <p>Science to policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to the European Commission's (DG-MARE) Provision of Scientific Advice for EU Fisheries Beyond EU waters (e.g. NAFO Joint Commission-Scientific Council Working Group on the Ecosystem Approach Framework to Fisheries Management (WG-EAFFM), Dartmouth (Canada), July 2019. bit.ly/3bSpU5e <p>Science to industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications: three articles published in local fisheries magazine, <i>Industrias Pesqueras</i>. industriaspesqueras.com <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Duran Muñoz P (2018) Pesquerías profundas y prospección de hidrocarburos en el Atlántico noroeste: Un ejercicio de Planificación Espacial Marina del proyecto ATLAS. <i>Industrias Pesqueras</i>, 2123, 48. Duran Muñoz P (2019) Gestión espacial integral en el Atlántico noroeste: ¿es posible compatibilizar las pesquerías de alta mar, la explotación de hidrocarburos "offshore" y la conservación de los ecosistemas? <i>Industrias Pesqueras</i>, 2144, 34-35. Duran Muñoz P (2020) Industria offshore de hidrocarburos, pesquerías del fletán negro y ecosistemas marinos vulnerables en el área NAFO: Conflictos emergentes y posibles soluciones. <i>Industrias Pesqueras</i>, 2166, 50-51. Engagement with NAFO contracting parties at NAFO Working Group meetings (e.g. WG-EAFFM July 2019) <p>Science to society</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media coverage: Covered by Spanish National Television, Canal 24h and Lab24 magazine. bit.ly/25xzyVB Articles in ATLAS Project Newsletter, Issue 5 (March 2019) and Issue 7 (February 2020). bit.ly/3FVGuGW Outreach events: European Researchers Night (2018, 2019), Vigo, Spain IEO-Vigo YouTube Channel: youtube.com/watch?v=BSWjwEwJg8
Impact	<p>Initial measures of impact (June 2020):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications: > 160 reads Newsletter readers: 200 + Audience at conferences and workshops (scientists, managers): 100 + Public engagement: 50 + <p>Longer term impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to ocean governance in the NAFO area Contribution to future revisions of EU Fisheries policies Contribution to UN Strategic Development Goal 14: Life below water
Take home message	The results contribute to providing a synoptic perspective on the state of NAFO ecosystems and supporting the implementation of ATLAS research in ocean management and governance. This work addresses, for the first time, the issue of seabed litter and current challenges facing MSP in the NAFO Regulatory Area. These include difficulties in assessing cumulative impact, tension between different regulatory frameworks that affect fisheries and hydrocarbon activities in ABNJ, and the lack of an appropriate authority needed to undertake MSP in the high seas.

ATLAS CONSORTIUM OF RESULTS - OBJECTIVE 4: DEVELOP

Next steps	The next steps for this work include applying the methodology to other areas and preparing similar advisory information for other regional management organisations. From a research perspective, ATLAS would like to continue this work, including cumulative impact assessments and using these methods to present similar cases in other areas.
Contact and contributors	Pablo Duran Muñoz and Mar Sacau (IEO) ATLAS Partners: IEO
More information	Horizon Results Platform: bit.ly/2XAVFKL

ATLAS HAS PROVIDED ANSWERS TO SOME OF THE MOST FUNDAMENTAL QUESTIONS ABOUT THE NATURE AND MAKE-UP OF OUR PRECIOUS AND ANCIENT MARINE ENVIRONMENTS, AT A TIME WHEN THEY ARE TRULY UNDER THREAT.

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ATLAS CONSORTIUM OF RESULTS - IMPACT AND LEGACY

IMPACT AND LEGACY

Healthy oceans and seas are central to our well-being and economic security. The North Atlantic Ocean harbours biologically rich deep-sea ecosystems that provide provisioning, regulatory and cultural services essential to Atlantic nations. To secure these services for future generations, ATLAS has made essential contributions to strengthening our knowledge base, developing innovative tools and applying a basin-scale approach to ocean management. This work is crucial for the North Atlantic's preservation and sustainable exploitation.

The results generated by ATLAS have, and will continue to:

1. **Unlock the potential of resources for the sustainable production of new products and industrial applications through improved management and governance.**
2. **Strengthen cooperation among EU Member States with respect to Atlantic ecosystem-based research, as well as with international partner countries.**
3. **Contribute to the implementation of the EU Integrated Maritime Policy, its environmental pillar the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), the EU Maritime Strategy for the Atlantic Ocean Area, and the Galway Statement on Atlantic Ocean Cooperation.**
4. **Contribute to the implementation of international agreements to conserve Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs).**

The collective approach to assessing deep-sea Atlantic ecosystems and the commitment to transferring new knowledge to industry and policy partners have been essential aspects of ATLAS' work. These activities ensure that ATLAS research will have a lasting impact beyond the project's duration.

Ocean science and Ocean Literacy

Europe's Marine and Maritime Research strategy is based on the premise that science and technology are key to sustainable marine economic growth, and the implementation of an ecosystem approach to management. ATLAS has been a strong contributor to this strategy, furthering several fields and branches of ocean science, generating 62 research outputs (May 2020) including 88 peer-reviewed publications and 106 data sets that contain new information, observations and measurements on key marine variables, and understanding on past variability and responses (see figure 1 and table 1 below). At the time of writing (June 2020), ATLAS had published 96 publications and an additional 105 were in preparation. The team has explored previously unknown areas of the deep Atlantic Ocean and made some of the biggest discoveries in ocean science this decade, including how we understand unprecedented rates of Atlantic Ocean circulation change in the industrial era, describing more than 30 benthic communities and discovering 12 new species. ATLAS results support researchers to produce more accurate predictions of marine ecosystems' response to future scenarios.

The collective approach of ATLAS has also facilitated cooperation amongst Atlantic Ocean researchers through trans-Atlantic initiatives such as ArcticNet expeditions, as well as engagement with sister projects (Sponges and MERCEs) and connections through the ATLAS consortium. The success of ATLAS collaborations will positively impact future Atlantic ecosystem-based research among EU member states and Atlantic nations through a range of initiatives (e.g. Atlantic).

Contributing to a globally ocean literate society, ATLAS initiated a new dialogue with the public and engaged them with the deep ocean. Through innovative education resources, media and communication campaigns, ATLAS has reached an estimated 105 million people. The ATLAS Educational Outreach portfolio has already been delivered to more than 34,000 people across Europe, been demonstrated to marine educators (European Marine Science Educators Association, Irish Ocean Literacy Network), and further contributes to the Ocean Literacy and Atlantic Action Plan aspects of ATLAS' legacy.

Ocean Management and Governance (Industry and Policy)

Supporting the development of adaptive and cross-sectoral management plans for sustainable exploitation and use of marine resource, ATLAS conducted the first basin-scale assessment of the North Atlantic Ocean. Transferring the results from this assessment and sharing new information with industrial stakeholders and active engagement with relevant Blue Growth industries (e.g. BP, BMT Cordah, DeepTrek, Equinor, Gardline, Hartley Anderson, Irish Offshore Operators Association, Marathon Oil, MEDIN, the Oil and Gas Innovation Centre, Shell, UK Department of Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy), as well as the ATLAS Advisory Board, Woods Hole and Canadian Natural Resources (samples obtained from the North Sea), has ensured the greatest impact of ATLAS research and longevity of ATLAS legacy.

ATLAS partners developed a strong science-policy interface from the beginning of the project, a key element for successfully informing future ocean governance measures. ATLAS results have influenced national, regional, and global level policy discussions, including the EU Integrated Maritime Policy (see figure 2). Implementing the ATLAS Geobase for geospatial data visualisation (with eventual ingestion of data to EMOBnet) and curating the ATLAS community space on Zenodo have enhanced marine knowledge and the European Commission's vision for "a seamless multi-resolution digital seabed map of European waters by 2020". ATLAS Blue Growth scenario testing has already begun to generate valuable insights as Member States develop and review maritime spatial plans under the MSFD. Furthermore, ATLAS revisions to Good Environmental Status assessments support the EU Integrated Maritime Policy, under the MSFD. Knowledge generated by ATLAS on the contribution of cold-water

Data Type	Research Topic	Parameter Type	Parameters	Methods	Regions	Static Maps	Dynamic Maps	
observations	biogeography	biological	1	1	1	1	0	
		biogeochemical	1	1	1	1	1	
		geomorphological	7	4	1	2	6	
	environmental conditions	physical	1	1	1	0	1	
		biogeochemical	1	1	1	0	1	
		human activity	Industry	1	2	1	2	0
modelling	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	4	2	1	4	9	
		geomorphological	7	4	6	6	1	
		physical	5	14	2	14	6	
	environmental processes	biogeochemical	1	2	1	2	2	
		habitat suitability	biological	12	4	1	0	48
		habitat distribution	ecological	1	1	5	5	0
experts assessment	connectivity	biological	1	4	13	12	4	
		conservation	status	4	2	2	0	4
	human activity	Industry	5	5	3	3	4	
		research	2	3	3	4	1	

Table 1: Summary of ATLAS data sets. Table adapted from ATLAS Deliverable D8.3 (Pérez S, Galera J, Collart T and Larkin K, 2020).

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - IMPACT AND LEGACY

corals to biogeochemical cycles highlight the importance of commitments to protect Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and support the MSFD and Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs). ATLAS has also developed useful tools that can be used by RFMOs to identify areas where VMEs are likely to occur.

ATLAS data contributed to the description of six features that meet the criteria of Ecologically or Biologically Sensitive Areas (EBSAs) during the Convention on Biological Diversity's Northeast Atlantic EBSA workshop (September 2019, Stockholm). Other ATLAS contributions to international policy include presentations of ATLAS results to delegates at the UN Intergovernmental Conferences on developing international legally binding instruments for the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction.

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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - IMPACT AND LEGACY

ATLAS POLICY LEGACY

NATIONAL	REGIONAL	GLOBAL
UK Sustainable Seas Inquiry	EU Integrated Marine Policy	BBNJ negotiations
Canadian EBSAs	EU MSFD	CBD EBSA Process
Azores MPA conservation targets	EU MSP Directive	2013 Galway Statement
	EU Common Fisheries Policy	ISA Mining Code
	Regional Fisheries Management	

Figure 2: ATLAS Policy Legacy. Figure adapted from ATLAS deliverable D7.8 (Timmer and Johnson, 2020).

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - LOOKING FORWARD

LOOKING FORWARD

The United Nations has proclaimed a **Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)** to support efforts to reverse the cycle of decline in ocean health and gather ocean stakeholders worldwide. As we approach this Decade and responding to the UN's call, the ATLAS project shares these key messages and makes the following recommendations:

- 1. Deep-sea observations:** Large-scale ocean exploration and management, as well as detailed deep-sea ecosystem studies require large volumes of high-quality observational data. ATLAS collaborators, for example with the Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program (OSNAP), have supported the collection of new and long-term measurements in areas where previously there were none. These measurements have revealed the true processes determining variability in Atlantic Ocean circulation patterns, contributing to fundamental baseline oceanography, and highlighting the importance of such observations. There is a need for coordinated systematic observation programmes (e.g. EDOs, GOOS) and research expeditions to support future deep-sea observations that underpin ocean science. As exemplified by the ATLAS approach, it is critically important that such coordinated observation programmes are strongly linked to ecological assessments and an improved understanding of the basic biology of key species. For example, substantial efforts are needed to understand the larval biology of deep-sea organisms so truly representative models can be built of their dispersal and connectivity.
- 2. Limitations and accuracy of past and future models:** ATLAS partners have found spatial and temporal scale issues with current climate models and identified knowledge gaps. Changes in North Atlantic Circulation are linked to increased greenhouse gas emissions and subsequent climate forcing. Using combined modelling approaches and palaeo reconstructions, ATLAS has improved our capacity to model future climate scenarios and highlighted limitations of past models. Past inaccuracies need to be recognised and new approaches incorporated into future climate scenarios. New models combining hydrodynamics and animal physiology are an effective tool to predict coral and sponge distribution, biomass and metabolic activity. In addition, species-specific connectivity models need to be considered as cold-water corals that have seemingly similar ecological roles can still differ in dispersal ability. ATLAS has shown that larval behaviour has a greater impact on connectivity than ocean current circulation in the North Atlantic, and that the lack of such behaviour data remains a key knowledge gap. Interactive effects of climate change that affect species survival (e.g. impact on food supply) need to be considered and should be prioritised for future research priorities. Finally, models that aggregate complex spatial information (e.g. by incorporating ecosystem connectivity metrics, habitat suitability models and the VME index) can provide useful inputs to decision making processes, and should be used to help to inform these processes.
- 3. Establishing Good Environmental Status (GES) in the deep sea:** Climate change will affect GES in the deep sea, with changing environmental conditions leading to shifts in species distributions and loss of suitable habitat. Assessing GES in the deep sea is challenging but essential for establishing monitoring programs and developing robust ocean governance measures. ATLAS has proposed a new definition of GES, that better addresses the specific characteristics of the deep sea, as well as a set of the most suitable indicators and threshold values for each indicator to appropriately assess GES in the deep sea. Future GES assessments should be carried out at habitat and ecosystem level (rather than species level) and at large spatial and temporal scales. These recommendations should be applied to future revisions of the European Commission's Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and could constitute a basis for deep-sea assessments, including in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ).
- 4. Shaping and unifying future research and policy initiatives in the Atlantic deep sea:** To ensure sustainable Blue Growth, there is a need for policy initiatives that focus on safeguarding biodiversity and the multitude of ecosystem services provided by the deep sea, in addition to basin-scale maritime spatial planning that minimises conflict. With many Blue Economy sectors anticipated to expand their activities by 2030, managing the cumulative impact of human activities (including climate change) is crucial for safeguarding biodiversity and other deep-sea ecosystem services. ATLAS has shown the importance of considering these services for future Blue Growth, Marine Spatial Planning in the deep sea, as well as the development of future frameworks designed to manage and conserve ecosystems and the services they provide. Monetary valuations are one tool that can identify some of the benefits from ecosystem services. ATLAS has also identified limitations in the functionality of current Area-Based Management Tools (ABMTs). There is a need for more complete impact assessments; however, creating a network to use current ABMTs in the North Atlantic could be a starting point to support short-term conservation efforts, and to inform future conservation priorities.
- 5. Engaging with public stakeholders and models for communication and knowledge transfer:** The public are legitimate stakeholders, with rights, responsibilities and obligations, who need to be involved in marine stewardship and governance. ATLAS has shown that, despite much of the public being unfamiliar with deep-sea ecosystems, there is societal support for new management plans that aim to improve environmental health and quality. The public's support and recognition of a need to protect deep-sea ecosystems reinforces the importance of Ocean Literacy efforts over the last decade, the continued need to engage with public stakeholders and for researchers to implement knowledge transfer of their results. There is a need to include the public's preferences and valuation into the conservation discussion related to the deep sea, and to align this with scientific efforts to secure biodiversity conservation across large marine spatial areas. Combining scientific efforts with management efforts and achieving successful and measurable transfer of research results can only be achieved if results are adopted and exploited by relevant end users, which requires a revision of current scientific communication models.

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BY INCREASING HUMANITY'S UNDERSTANDING OF THE DEEP ATLANTIC, ATLAS HAS THE WELL-BEING, PROSPERITY, AND SECURITY OF OUR WORLD AT ITS HEART.

ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - GLOSSARY	ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - RESOURCES AND LINKS
<p>GLOSSARY</p>	<p>RESOURCES AND LINKS</p>
<p>ABMT Area Based Management Tool</p> <p>ABNJ Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction</p> <p>AMOC Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation</p> <p>AORA Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance</p> <p>BG Blue Growth</p> <p>CBD Convention on Biological Diversity</p> <p>CICES Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services</p> <p>CWC Cold-Water Coral</p> <p>DWS Deep-Water Sponge</p> <p>EBSA Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas</p> <p>ESS Ecosystem Summary Sheets</p> <p>FAO Food and Agriculture Organization</p> <p>GFCM-FAO General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean</p> <p>GES Good Environmental Status</p> <p>ICES International Council for the Exploration of the Sea</p> <p>ILBI International Legally Binding Instrument</p> <p>IPBES Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services</p> <p>IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change</p> <p>ISA International Seabed Authority</p> <p>JNCC Joint Nature Conservation Committee</p> <p>MESMA Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Areas</p> <p>MPA Marine Protected Area</p> <p>MSFD Marine Strategy Framework Directive</p> <p>MSP Maritime Spatial Planning</p> <p>NEAFC North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission</p> <p>NAFO Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization</p> <p>NEAT Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool</p> <p>OECD Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development</p> <p>OL Ocean Literacy</p> <p>OSNAP Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program</p> <p>OSPAR Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic</p>	<p>ATLAS publications</p> <p>ATLAS partners have published 66 new research articles to date (June 2020), with 105 more currently in preparation or in press. All ATLAS publications are open access and a full list of articles can be found on the ATLAS website: eu-atlas.org/resources/atlas-library#Publications</p> <p>ATLAS deliverables</p> <p>All ATLAS project deliverables, which have been approved by the European Commission and are not confidential, are available on the ATLAS website eu-atlas.org/resources/atlas-library#deliverables</p> <p>ATLAS submissions to the Horizon Results Platform</p> <p>ATLAS has submitted 18 results to the European Commission's Horizon Results Platform (June 2020). All results are available from the EC Funding & tender opportunities portal and a list of results can be found on the ATLAS website www.eu-atlas.org/resources/horizon-results-platform</p> <p>ATLAS communication and outreach resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATLAS newsletters: eu-atlas.org/news/browse-previous-newsletters • ATLAS factsheet in English, Dutch, Spanish, Portuguese: eu-atlas.org/resource/public-documents <p>• ATLAS brochure: eu-atlas.org/resources/public-documents/215-atlas-brochure</p> <p>• ATLAS outreach resources: eu-atlas.org/education/public-engagement</p> <p>• ATLAS education packs: eu-atlas.org/education/education-packs</p> <p>• ATLAS augmented reality colouring sheets: eu-atlas.org/education/spectacular-colouring-pages</p> <p>• ATLAS animal flow chart: eu-atlas.org/education/which-deep-sea-creature-are-you</p> <p>ATLAS data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geospatial data on the ATLAS Geonode: atlas-horizon2020.eu/ • ATLAS on the European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects (EDMERP): edmerp.seadatanet.org/report/12416 • ATLAS on European MSP Platform: msp-platform.eu/projects/eu-atlas-trans-atlantic-assessment-and-deep-water-ecosystem-based-spatial-management • Data ingestion to EMODnet (expected completion: July 2021) emodnet.eu
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ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - NEW DEEP-SEA SPECIES	ATLAS COMPENDIUM OF RESULTS - CONTACTS AND CONTRIBUTORS																																						
<p>NEW DEEP-SEA SPECIES</p>	<p>CONTACTS AND CONTRIBUTORS</p>																																						
<p>ATLAS has contributed to the identification of at least 12 new or putative new species and 35 new records at the ATLAS case study 7: Gulf of Cadiz, Strait of Gibraltar, Alboran Sea, case study 8: Azores and case study 10: Davis Strait, Eastern Arctic. The table below outlines confirmed new records as of June 2020, however additional descriptions are expected.</p> <p>More information: ATLAS deliverable 3.3 bit.ly/2WKLZLO Contact Person: Telmo Morato IMAR-UJAZ, Marina Carreiro-Silva, IMAR-UJAZ; José Rueda, IEO; Ellen Kørnchington, DFO.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Project Coordinator</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>J Murray Roberts, UEDIN</td> <td>murrayroberts@ed.ac.uk</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">Project Manager</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Julia Eilteen, UEDIN</td> <td>EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">Steering Committee</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Stuart Cunningham, SAMS <i>Work Package Leader on Ocean dynamics driving ecosystem response</i></td> <td>Stuart.Cunningham@sams.ac.uk</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dick van Oevelen, NIOZ <i>Work Package Leader on Functional Ecosystems</i></td> <td>Dick.van.Oevelen@nioz.nl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Telmo Morato, IMAR-UJAZ <i>Work Package Leader on Biodiversity and Biogeography</i></td> <td>tmorato@gmail.com</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sophie Arnaud Haond, IFREMER <i>Work Package Leader on Connected Resources</i></td> <td>sarnaud@ifremer.fr</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Claire Armstrong, UIT <i>Work Package Leader on Valuing Ecosystems Services and Blue Growth Potential</i></td> <td>claire.armstrong@uit.no</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Anthony Grehan, NUIG <i>Work Package Leader on Maritime Spatial Planning</i></td> <td>anthony.grehan@nuigalway.ie</td> </tr> <tr> <td>David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd <i>Work Package Leader on Policy Integration to Inform Key Agreements</i></td> <td>david.johnson@seascopeconsultants.co.uk</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Stéphane Pesant, UniHB <i>Work Package leader on Open Science Resources for Stakeholders</i></td> <td>spesant@marum.de</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Marieke Reever, AquatT <i>Work Package Leader on Dissemination, Knowledge Transfer and Outreach</i></td> <td>marieke@aquat.tue.nl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Lea-Anne Henry, UEDIN <i>Case-studies coordinator</i></td> <td>L.Henry@ed.ac.uk</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">Advisory Board</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Jake Rice, DFO (Emeritus) <i>Advisory Board Chair</i></td> <td>Jake.Rice@dfo-mpo.gc.ca</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ingunn Nilsen, Equinor</td> <td>innil@equinor.com</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Anders Hermansen, Equinor</td> <td>andhe@equinor.com</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Project Coordinator		J Murray Roberts, UEDIN	murrayroberts@ed.ac.uk	Project Manager		Julia Eilteen, UEDIN	EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk	Steering Committee		Stuart Cunningham, SAMS <i>Work Package Leader on Ocean dynamics driving ecosystem response</i>	Stuart.Cunningham@sams.ac.uk	Dick van Oevelen, NIOZ <i>Work Package Leader on Functional Ecosystems</i>	Dick.van.Oevelen@nioz.nl	Telmo Morato, IMAR-UJAZ <i>Work Package Leader on Biodiversity and Biogeography</i>	tmorato@gmail.com	Sophie Arnaud Haond, IFREMER <i>Work Package Leader on Connected Resources</i>	sarnaud@ifremer.fr	Claire Armstrong, UIT <i>Work Package Leader on Valuing Ecosystems Services and Blue Growth Potential</i>	claire.armstrong@uit.no	Anthony Grehan, NUIG <i>Work Package Leader on Maritime Spatial Planning</i>	anthony.grehan@nuigalway.ie	David Johnson, Seascope Consultants Ltd <i>Work Package Leader on Policy Integration to Inform Key Agreements</i>	david.johnson@seascopeconsultants.co.uk	Stéphane Pesant, UniHB <i>Work Package leader on Open Science Resources for Stakeholders</i>	spesant@marum.de	Marieke Reever, AquatT <i>Work Package Leader on Dissemination, Knowledge Transfer and Outreach</i>	marieke@aquat.tue.nl	Lea-Anne Henry, UEDIN <i>Case-studies coordinator</i>	L.Henry@ed.ac.uk	Advisory Board		Jake Rice, DFO (Emeritus) <i>Advisory Board Chair</i>	Jake.Rice@dfo-mpo.gc.ca	Ingunn Nilsen, Equinor	innil@equinor.com	Anders Hermansen, Equinor	andhe@equinor.com
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This booklet was designed and developed by AquaTT, with significant contributions from ATLAS partners. All results described were generated by the ATLAS project. Content writing, compilation, editing, design and infographic development was carried out by AquaTT – Annette Wilson, Peadar O'Riada, Kegan Porter, Sive Finlay, Anne-Marie Williams and Marieke Reuver, with input from the ATLAS Project Office (UEDIN), Julia Eighnen, Georgios Kazanidis, J. Murray Roberts and result owners.

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Annex 1 – ATLAS KER’s submissions to the Horizon Results Platform

ATLAS has submitted eighteen Key Exploitable Results to the European Commission’s Horizon Results Platform (status: June 2020). All results are available from the EC Funding & tender opportunities portal and a list of results can also be found on the **ATLAS** website www.eu-atlas.org/resources/horizon-results-platform

Key Exploitable Result	Owner	Link
Weakening of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) through the industrial era	David Thornalley (UCL)	bit.ly/2To3K1f
An expert assessment of risks posed by climate change and anthropogenic activities to ecosystem services in the deep-sea	Claire Armstrong (UiT)	bit.ly/2lvRlgd
Atlantic Adventures with ATLAS - The ATLAS educational outreach portfolio	Hermione Cockburn (Dynamic Earth)	bit.ly/2x745g0
Cold-water coral and sponge physiology database	Covadonga Orejas (IEO) Evert De Froe, Dick van Oevelen (NIOZ)	bit.ly/2NHnzx0
New approach to identify the key environmental parameters that control cold-water coral ecosystem performance	Dierk Hebbeln (MARUM – UniHB)	bit.ly/2VpYR8O
Using eDNA and quantitative PCR to assess biodiversity in the open ocean	Laura Gargan, Jens Carlsson (UCD)	bit.ly/3eMR9wG
Approaching the assessment of Good Environmental Status in the deep-sea	Covadonga Orejas (IEO) Georgios Kazanidis (UEDIN)	bit.ly/2CVSjyB
Current deep-sea Area-Based Management Tools are unprepared for climate change	David Johnson (Seascope Consultants Ltd)	bit.ly/2XTnSuR
New evidence to support the protection of deep-sea sponge ecosystems at Tropic Seamount	Berta Ramiro-Sánchez, Lea-Anne Henry (UEDIN)	bit.ly/2RZOW7N
Novel Marine Spatial Planning decision support protocol	Anthony Grehan, Oisín Callery (NUIG)	bit.ly/2Zn9YQG
New climate model projects major impacts on coral and commercially important fish habitats in the deep Atlantic due to climate change	Telmo Morato (IMAR-UAz)	bit.ly/3eJ81o5
Contribution to the development of NAFO Ecosystem Summary Sheets	Pablo Durán Muñoz, Mar Sacau (IEO)	bit.ly/2NE2UK5

ATLAS GeoNode marine data visualization tool	Kate Larkin, Tim Collart (Seascope Belgium)	bit.ly/3c0n6A8
ATLAS Policy Brief on MPA network design	Rob Tinch (Iodine) David Johnson (Seascope Consultants Ltd)	bit.ly/37EJBta
Low-cost imaging systems to observe the deep sea	Carlos Dominguez Carrió, Telmo Morato (IMAR-UAz)	bit.ly/38ceDZH
New approach to map coral reef biomass and its usefulness to derive ecosystem functions	Laurence De Clippele, J Murray Roberts (UEDIN)	bit.ly/3idy3ID
A non-invasive method to quantify oxygen uptake by cold-water corals (CWC)	Lorenzo Rovelli, Ronnie N. Glud (USD)	bit.ly/31vX31p
New deep-sea species discovered by ATLAS	Telmo Morato, Marina Carreiro-Silva (IMAR-UAz) José Rueda (IEO) Ellen Kenchington (DFO)	bit.ly/3eL7dzh

Final Page: Document Information

EU Project N°	678760	Acronym	ATLAS
Full Title	A trans-Atlantic assessment and deep-water ecosystem-based spatial management plan for Europe		
Project website	www.eu-atlas.org		

Deliverable	N°	D9.5	Title	Knowledge Transfer Activity Report 2
Work Package	N°	9	Title	Dissemination, Knowledge Transfer and Outreach

Date of delivery	Contractual	30.06.2020 (M50)	Actual	30.06.2020 (M50)
Dissemination level	x	PU Public, fully open, e.g. web		
		CO Confidential restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement		
		CI Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC		

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Version log			
Issue Date	Revision N°	Author	Change
22.06.20	V1	Annette Wilson, Marieke Reuver (AquaTT)	Version 1 drafted; reviewed by ATLAS Project Office (UEDIN) Julia Eighteen, J Murray Roberts
29.06.20	V2	Annette Wilson, Marieke Reuver (AquaTT)	Minor corrections and edits to text including feedback from UEDIN; screenshots of Compendium updated; links to KERs submitted to Horizon Results Platform added.
30.09.20	V3	Annette Wilson, Marieke Reuver (AquaTT)	Screenshots of Compendium updated.